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INTEGRAL UNIVERSITY
LUCKNOW (INDIA)

DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTER APPLICATION
TECHNICAL COMMITTEE

Presents

JANUARY-23

MONTHLY
Tech Dose

WELCOME TO DIGITAL AND TECHNICAL WORLD

INTEGRAL UNIVERSITY

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01

Microsoft And Amazon To Layoff A Total Of 28,000 Employees

On January 18, Microsoft's CEO, Satya Nadella, announced significant layoffs at the company. In a statement, Nadella said, "today, we are making changes that will result in the reduction of our overall workforce by 10,000 jobs through the end of FY23 Q3. This represents less than 5 percent of our total employee base, with some notifications happening today". While Microsoft is laying off around 10,000 people, Amazon is laying off an astounding total of 18,000 people. This combined number includes layoffs in November 2022. The cuts represent approximately 6% of Amazon's workforce. However, most of the eliminated roles are connected to the Amazon Stores and PXT divisions.

<https://zeenews.india.com/technology/windows-11-to-let-users-connect-to-android-phones-via-hotspot-2528142.html>

02

Data of 200 million twitter users leaked

Hackers stole the email addresses of more than 200 million Twitter users and posted them on an online hacking forum, a security researcher said on Wednesday, 4 January 2023. The breach "will unfortunately lead to a lot of hacking, targeted phishing and doxxing", Alon Gal, co-founder of Israeli cybersecurity monitoring firm Hudson Rock, wrote on LinkedIn. He called it "one of the most significant leaks I've seen". Twitter has taken to investigate or remediate the issue. Reuters could not independently verify if the data on the forum was authentic and came from Twitter. Screenshots of the hacker forum, where the data appeared and have circulated online.

<https://inbold.com/tiktok-becomes-the-worlds-highest-grossing-social-app-with-over-2-5-million-in-daily-revenue/>

03

Samsung Galaxy S23 Ultra will reportedly feature night vision camera

One of the most anticipated new smartphones this year, the Galaxy S23 series is about to be announced. The Galaxy S23 Ultra will feature a night vision camera and also feature a pair of 12MP cameras and a 2MP sensor. A 12MP image sensor will also be used for the front-facing camera. It isn't clear where the improvement to night photography will come from. The device will record 8K video at 30 frames per second (FPS).

<https://www.indiatimes.com/trending/wtf/woman-scammed-by-fake-russian-astronaut-loses-rs-24-lakh-581769.html>

Tesla has been slapped with a \$2 million fine in South Korea

South Korea's antitrust regulator fined Tesla 2.85 billion won (\$2.2 million) for false advertising, saying the company overstated the range of its cars in cold weather, as reported by multiple outlets including Reuters. The Korea Fair Trade Commission said at a press conference that Tesla exaggerated the driving range of its electric vehicles, failing to inform customers that cars have shorter driving ranges in lower temperatures.

<https://www.indiatoday.in/technology/news/story/netflix-to-charge-extra-fee-from-users-for-sharing-their-passwords-2287129-2022-10-19>

05

Whatsapp announces new proxy support feature

Meta Platforms Inc's WhatsApp said users of the messaging app will now be able to use proxy servers to access the service in countries where the app is blocked. A proxy server is an intermediary between users and web services and acts as a web filter that allow netizens to circumvent restrictions and censorship. WhatsApp said proxy support on the app is now officially available for users with the latest version.

<https://indianexpress.com/article/technology/tech/jio-true-5g-powered-wifi-launched-in-india-all-you-need-to-know-8224808/>

06 Tata to start manufacturing iPhones in India

Tata Group will soon start manufacturing iPhones in India because the company is almost all set to acquire a major plant in the southern part of the country. The company wants to take over Wistron's iPhone Karnataka factory and it has been in talks with this Taiwanese company for months now. It has now come to light that Tata Group will complete the deal by the end of March.

<https://www.outlookindia.com/business/rbi-launches-concept-note-to-create-awareness-about-central-bank-digital-currency-cbdc--news-228283>

TCS rolls out 100% variable pay for majority of the workforce

Tata Consultancy Services (TCS), India's largest IT services exporter, has rolled out 100 per cent variable pay for employees up to C2 grade, while employees above the grade would be awarded variable pay as per business performance, for the third quarter of FY 2022-23. An email sent from the office of the Chief Human Resource Officer of the company, Milind Lakkad, read, "A decision has been taken to pay 100 percent of the quarterly variable pay (QVA) to all employees up to C2 or equivalent grades covered under this plan."

<https://www.hindustantimes.com/technology/modi-govt-s-warning-for-zoom-users-shouldn-t-be-ignored-at-any-cost-101665656226524.html>

08 Future Google TV to get self charging and a battery free remote

TW Electronics, the UK-based company behind the reference remote used on most Android TV and Google TV devices in recent years, has introduced a new design of the remote that includes a photovoltaic panel at the bottom that allows for self-charging of the battery. According to 9 to 5 Google, the panel used in the remote uses light sources to convert that energy into electricity that can charge the battery within the device.

<https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/tech/information-tech/wipro-infosys-tech-mahindra-revoke-offer-letters-given-to-freshers-reports/articleshow/94624440.cms?from=mdr>

09 Swiggy rolls out ambulance service for delivery partners

Swiggy has been rolling out ambulance feature for its delivery partners and can reach the ambulance service instantly by tapping the SOS button on the partner app or through a toll-free number. The current average response time is 12 minutes. The programme was launched a few weeks after a Swiggy delivery partner lost his life in Noida after his scooter and a car collided.

https://www.business-standard.com/article/technology/akasa-air-uses-artificial-intelligence-product-to-make-travel-affordable-122093000254_1.html

Microsoft AI tool VALL-E can clone your voice from a 3-second audio

The tech world has always been fascinated by Artificial Intelligence and has highlighted its negative, as well as positive effects from time to time. Microsoft's AI program, VALL-E, has been in the limelight for its capability of cloning a voice from a 3-second audio. Microsoft introduced the program as 'a language modeling approach for text to speech synthesis (TTS)' on their demo website, created to show VALL-E's capabilities. There are ample examples showcasing VALL-E's abilities on the website.

<https://www.businesstoday.in/technology/news/story/whatsapp-services-affected-across-the-world-35077-2022-10-25>

11 Wikipedia desktop gets a new look after more than 10 years

Wikipedia is finally giving its desktop interface an updated design its first in over 10 years. The site is rolling out the new look now across most Wikipedia pages. The site initially announced the redesign in 2020, with plans to implement it by the end of 2021. It's unclear why the update was further delayed; the Wikimedia Foundation has said only that the redesign was a "long and complex process." But the goal has been to improve the overall browsing experience with incremental tweaks here and there, developed with user feedback.

<https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/business/india-business/tata-power-hit-by-cyber-attack-says-company/articleshow/94865348.cms>

12

Asia's richest man Gautam Adani is addicted to ChatGPT

Asia's richest man Gautam Adani says he is addicted to ChatGPT, the powerful new AI tool that interacts with users in convincing and conversational way. In a LinkedIn post last week, the India tycoon said that the release of ChatGPT was a "transformational moment in the democratization of AI given its astounding capabilities as well as comical failures". The billionaire admitted to "some addiction" to ChatGPT since he has started using it.

<https://www.indiatoday.in/technology/news/story/fired-by-elon-musk-twitter-ceo-parag-agrawal-and-policy-chief-vijaya-gadde-set-to-get-around-rs-1000-crore-2290887-2022-10-29>

Users can now send 62 words per minute using new Brain-Computer Interface

13

A team of Stanford scientists claims to have tested a new brain-computer interface (BCI) that can decode speech at up to 62 words per minute, a 3.4-fold improvement on the previous record. This would be a big step towards real-time speech conversion at the speed of natural human conversation. Max Hodak, who founded the BCI company Neuralink with Elon Musk but was not involved in the study, called the research "a meaningful step change in the utility of implanted BCIs" in an email to Futurism.

<https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/industry/banking/finance/india-saw-20-5-bn-online-transactions-worth-rs-36-trillion-in-q2/articleshow/94638319.cms?from=mdr>

14

Indian government is planning to make Indian rupee the International Currency

The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) has enabled exports and imports to be denominated in rupees. This will internationalise the rupee which, in turn, will reduce foreign currency risks for traders and help navigate payment hurdles in trading with Russia. It will also reduce demand for dollars. The new framework provides for a market-determined exchange rate between two trading partners.

<https://indiaexpress.com/article/technology/science/researchers-are-trying-to-teach-a-robot-how-to-laugh-to-improve-human-robot-conversations-8161917#:~:text=Researchers%20at%20the%20University%20of%20Cork%20are%20using%20AI%20to%20teach%20robots%20to%20laugh,Frontiers%20in%20AI%20Robotics%20and%20AI>

15

8 year old Rishi Shiv who received bal puraskar has higher IQ than Albert Einstien

Rishi Shiv Prasanna, an eight year old kid from Bengaluru, has received the prestigious Pradhan Mantri Rashtriya Bal Puraskar Award. Prasanna received the award from President Droupadi Murmu for inventing three Android applications at such a young age. Notably, Prasanna has a higher IQ than Albert Einstein, and has a validated IQ of 180, which is greater than Albert Einstein's and far higher than the normal standard of 130 for very bright people. Since the age of five, the eight-year-old has had an interest in coding. He created three apps: "IQ Test App" for youngsters, "Countries of the World", and "CHB."

<https://www.theverge.com/2022/10/24/2342716/google-chrome-windows-7-8-1-end-support>

Unknown Facts

Motorola produced the first-ever portable mobile phone.

Japan has the fastest Internet speed of 319 terabits per second.

Combining all the bitcoin mining operations worldwide is equivalent to the computing power of 3.7 million supercomputers.

An average person can blink seven times every minute when using a computer.

Jeff Bezos named his company Cadabra Inc before renaming it Amazon.

Did You Know

News of the Month

Chat GPT

Chat GPT is an AI chatbot auto-generative system created by Open AI for online customer care. It is a pre-trained generative chat, which makes use of Natural Language Processing (NLP). The source of its data is textbooks, websites, and various articles, which it uses to model its own language for responding to human interaction. Chat GPT is a highly popular AI-based program that people use for generating dialogues. The chatbot has a language-based model that the developer fine-tunes for human interaction in a conversational manner.

It's a simulated chatbot primarily designed for customer service; people use it for various other purposes. These range from writing essays to generating code.

GPT-3 (Generative Pretrained Transformer 3) is a state-of-the-art language processing AI model developed by OpenAI. It is capable of generating human-like text and has a wide range of applications, including language translation, language modelling, and generating text for applications such as chatbots. It is one of the largest and most powerful language processing AI models to date, with 175 billion parameters.

What is GPT3

The main feature of Chat GPT is generating responses like those humans would provide, in a text box. Therefore, it is suitable for chatbots, AI system conversations, and virtual assistants. It can also give natural answers to questions in a conversational tone, and can generate stories and poems.

Features of Chat GPT

World's Top CEO

Jensen Huang
Nvidia

Mukesh Ambani
Reliance

Satya Nadella
Microsoft

Shantanu Narayan
Adobe

Sundar Pichai
Google

Punit Renjen
Deloitte

Estee Lauder
Fabrizio Freda

N. Chandrasekaran
Tata

Piyush Gubta
OBS

Top Programmers in the World of All Time

Dennis Ritchie
Father of C programming language

Linus Torvalds
Developer of Linux Operating systems

Bjarne Stroustrup
Developer of C++

James Gosling
Developer of JAVA

Tim Berners-Lee
Founder of HTML, URL and HTTP

Donald Knuth
Father of Analysis of Algorithms

Ken Thompson
Developer of Unix Operating systems

Brian Wilson Kernighan
Coauthor of the AWK and AMPL
programming languages.

Richard Stallman
Developer of GNU compiler

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01

UK Drone company performs First Microgravity Experiment

A British startup has successfully provided a first-of-its-kind microgravity service using a drone. The firm, called Gravitilab, flew its specially-modified LOUIS UAV quadcopter to an altitude of 2,000 feet (600 meters) before purposefully dropping a capsule carrying scientific experiments. The drop caused the capsule's contents to experience weightlessness for roughly five seconds. During that time, sensors took readings of the scientific payloads. Scientists have long used ground-based drop towers to achieve weightlessness for a brief moment, allowing them to study particles and objects under the effects of microgravity.

03

Telegram adds real-time message translation in its new update

Telegram Messenger has added major features in its latest update to its application, including Translating Entire Chats, Profile Picture Maker, Emoji Categories etc. With the "Translating Entire Chats" feature, premium users will be able to translate entire chats, groups and channels in real-time by tapping the Translate bar at the top. However, all users can translate individual messages by selecting them and tapping "Translate".

02

Tech Mahindra to open its first data, AI and cloud centre in Saudi Arabia

Tech Mahindra said on Wednesday, February 8 that it has signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the Ministry of Communication and Information Technology of Saudi Arabia to set up a data, AI, and cloud centre of excellence (CoE) in Riyadh. The data & AI and cloud CoE will enable accelerated and sustainable adoption of data analytics and ethical AI. It will further drive cloud-enabled transformation across industries to develop local assets, intellectual property (IP) and promote a cognitive approach across smart services to contribute to Saudi Vision 2030's digital-led transformation objectives

04

India's First AI-Based Chatbot "Lexi" Introduced in India

India recently launched its first AI-based chatbot named Lexi powered by ChatGPT which is a complex computer machine. The chatbot has been invented by the financial technology firm Velocity. This chatbot is designed to provide assistance to e-Commerce founders with business insights in a simplified manner. Moreover, it has been integrated with Velocity's own analytics tool i.e. Velocity Insights.

05

Microsoft uses ChatGPT to instruct robots, drones

Microsoft has conducted research to see if people can use ChatGPT to instruct robots without knowing programming languages or understanding robotics systems. After ChatGPT was given access to object-detection and object-distance data via application interfaces, the Microsoft researchers investigated its ability to generate code, mostly in Python, for robotics scenarios such as zero-shot planning and code generation.

06 US nominates ex Mastercard CEO Ajay Banga to head World Bank

United States President Joe Biden has nominated former Mastercard CEO Ajay Banga to become president of the World Bank, hailing his business experience in his native India and his commitment to mobilizing private funds to help developing countries grapple with climate change. The World Bank said on Wednesday, 22nd February that it expects to select a new president by early May to replace David Malpass, who announced his resignation last week after months of controversy over his views on climate change and pressure by US Treasury Secretary Janet Yellen for him to adopt “bolder and more imaginative” reforms.

07 OpenAI introduced tool to detect AI generated text including from ChatGPT

OpenAI, the world-renowned Artificial Intelligence research organization, has recently announced the launch of its latest AI tool, the AI Text Classifier. This AI tool is intended to recognize and distinguish content created by the popular language model ChatGPT from the human-written text. The features of the language model have been used in a variety of applications, including chatbots, automated content production, and even language translation.

08 Paytm's UPI Lite will now let users make payments without using PIN

- Paytm, the popular payments app, has introduced a new feature called UPI Lite that makes it easier for users to make small value transactions without needing to enter a PIN every time. With more than 50 per cent of transactions through UPI below Rs 200, UPI LITE will successfully provide a distributed way of authorizing low value transactions, moving them away from core banking.

09 Ola, Uber and Rapido bike taxi services banned in Delhi

The Delhi government announced ban on bike taxis with immediate effect. The decision will affect cab aggregators such as Ola, Uber, and Rapido, which are popular in the city. The Delhi transport department says that two-wheelers having non-transport (private) registration marks/numbers are being used to carry passengers. The government notice indicates that using personal vehicles as commercial taxis violates Motor Vehicle Act, 1988. The move will also affect many customers that rely on two-wheelers via Ola, Uber, and Rapido amid surging fares of cabs.

10 AI-powered Bing refuses to write job letter, calls it unethical

Bing, Microsoft's latest AI-powered tool, made headlines when it refused to write a cover letter for a job application. The AI system declined the task because it would be “unethical” and “unfair to other applicants.” Bing is an AI writing tool from Microsoft that uses advanced algorithms to assist users with their writing tasks. The tool can write articles, essays, and even emails. However, it appears that writing a cover letter for a job application goes against the company's principles of fairness and impartiality.

11 Facebook, Instagram Begin Rolling Out Paid Verification Service in Australia, New Zealand

Facebook and Instagram began a week-long rollout of their first paid verification service, testing users' willingness to pay for social media features that until now have been free. Facing a drop in advertising revenues, parent company Meta is piloting a subscription in Australia and New Zealand before it appears in larger markets. The service will cost \$11.99 (roughly Rs. 990) on the web and \$14.99 (roughly Rs. 1,240) on the iOS and Android mobile platforms.

12 Telangana Government Joins Forces With Bharat Web3 to Boost Blockchain Initiatives

Web³

The Telangana government has signed a memorandum of understanding (MoU) with the Bharat Web3 Association to stir discussions around the blockchain technology. The India-centric crypto advocacy organisation, that was formed in November 2022, has crypto players like CoinSwitch Kuber and WazirX among others as participatory members. As part of this fresh partnership, the Telangana government is looking at creating a nurturing ecosystem for Web3 developers and players to boost the growth of the overall blockchain industry.

India saw 20.5 billion online transactions worth Rs 36 trillion in Q2

India saw 20.57 billion online transactions worth Rs 36.08 trillion in the second quarter (Q2) this year. The online transactions were processed through debit and credit cards, prepaid payment instruments like mobile wallets and prepaid cards and UPI which includes P2M (person to merchant) and P2P (person to person) transactions. "UPI P2P accounted for 49 per cent in volume and 67 per cent in value but in terms of merchants' transaction. Transactions volume and value have seen an increase about 118 per cent increase in volume and over 98 per cent increase in value in Q2 2022 as compared to Q2 2021. UPI now has 346 partner banks as a part of the ecosystem. It is now accepted in countries like the UAE, Singapore, France and Bhutan.

14 Indian government blocked 232 Betting and Loan apps that are linked to China and other countries

The government has blocked 232 apps operated by overseas entities, including Chinese for being involved in betting, gambling and unauthorised loan service. Ministry of Electronics and IT (MeitY) has issued orders to block these apps following instructions from Ministry of Home Affairs. The order to block 138 apps that were involved in betting, gambling and money laundering were issued last evening. Separately, an order to block 94 apps engaged in unauthorised loan service has also been issued. They were posing a threat to the economic stability of the country.

15 Google will soon allow Users to delete 15 minutes history on Android

- Google Chrome is set to introduce a 'quick delete' option to its Android app. This would allow users to quickly clear their browsing history and cache from the last 15 minutes. On the desktop version of the browser, Chrome currently gives the following options - Last hour, 24 hours, 7 days, 4 weeks, and all time. With the 15-minute feature, Android users will get even more control and convenience over their web history. The feature is expected to be available in the upcoming version of Chrome for Android, currently in development.

android

Unknown Facts

In 1971, the first ever computer virus was developed. Named Creeper, it was made as an experiment just to see how it spread between computers. The virus simply displayed the message: "I'm the creeper, catch me if you can!"

QWERTY keyboard was designed to slow down the typing speed

Google's First Tweet was in binary. Google's first tweet was in 2009, and it was gibberish to most. Translated from binary to English, it reads, "I'm feeling lucky".

**DID
YOU
KNOW?**

News of the Month

WhatsApp will soon give 15 minutes to fix all the errors

When it comes to WhatsApp, it is one of the most popular instant messaging platforms in the world as it is being used by more than 2 billion users across the globe. WhatsApp is reportedly working on a feature that will give users up to 15 minutes to edit their messages to fix errors, if any, or add additional information to the original message. In addition to this, the Meta-owned platform will also show a message if the feature is not supported by the WhatsApp version on your smartphone. If you are using an older version of the instant messaging service that is not compatible with this ability, users will get the message 'You can see the edited message if you're on the latest version of WhatsApp.'

HOW IT WORKS

WABetaInfo said, WhatsApp beta for iOS 23.4.0.72 – which brings this 'edit message feature' – also fixes a crash that prevented users from playing within chats and status in the previous WhatsApp beta for iOS 23.4.0.70 update. For the timelines, the ability to edit messages in up to 15 minutes, meanwhile, will be released in a future update of the app. This new edit feature comes in handy if you want to fix any spelling or grammatical mistakes or add or remove some information. It appears that this feature is still under development but was recently spotted on WhatsApp beta for iOS 23.4.0.72, which was released for those enrolled in the TestFlight program.

TOP 10 CRYPTOCURRENCIES

Learning Channels & Websites

YOUTUBE CHANNELS

CodeWithHarry
Anuj Bhaiya
Apni Kaksha
Jenny's Lecture
Gate Smashers
Bhagwan Singh Vishwakarma
Telusko
MySirG.com
Programming with Mosh
freecodecamp.org
Traversy Media
Derek Banas
Clever Programming
thenewboston
LearnCode.academy
mycodeaschool

www.w3schools.com
www.geeksforgeeks.org
www.programiz.com
www.studytonight.com
www.javatpoint.com
www.freecodecamp.org
www.sololearn.com
www.tutorialspoint.com
www.guru99.com

CODING PRACTISE

www.hackerrank.com
www.topcoder.org
www.codechef.com
www.coderbyte.com
www.leetcode.com
www.hackerearth.org
www.exercism.io
www.interviewbit.com

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01

AKTU makes robot that works on finger gestures

Dr APJ Abdul Kalam Technical University (AKTU) has made a robot that can be instructed using the fingers of both hands by using machine learning technology. The robots will not only move on finger gestures but will also perform all work assigned as programmed. Differently abled people, especially visually impaired, deaf and mute, and senior citizens can use the robot for performing various tasks. The technology has been developed by the associate dean innovation and incubation centre, AKTU Anuj Sharma and his student team. For example, the robot whose information is recorded on the thumb will be turned on. Similarly, robots will work on other fingers as well

https://www.gadgetsnow.com/tech-news/apple-ceo-tim-cook-hits-europe-for-a-full-fledged-four-key-details/articleshow/94512633.cms?referrer=amp_articlelist

02

Twitter launches new API with free, basic, enterprise tiers

The company shared the information on Twitter via its Twitter Dev account: "Today we are launching our new Twitter API access tiers! We're excited to share more details about our self-serve access." Initially, the company had planned to shut down free access to its API on February 9, but later extended the deadline to February 13 and then again postponed it. Moreover, these three levels include a basic free level primarily intended for content posting bots, a \$100 per month basic level, and an expensive enterprise level. In addition, subscribing to any level gets access to Ads API at no additional cost, according to the company.

<https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/tech/information-tech/tcs-poised-to-seal-likely-2-billion-deal-for-bnsl-4g/articleshow/94542008.cms>

03

Google starts testing generative AI features in Gmail, Docs

Google has now started public testing them the upcoming generative artificial intelligence (AI) features Gmail and Docs. The current trusted test programme includes consumer, enterprise and education users (over 18 years) in the US, reports 9To5Google. This "small group" is invited by the tech giant to join and they must sign up and opt-in. The testers can also leave the programme at any time. Users in the programme can use generative AI in Gmail to draft everything from a birthday invitation to a job cover letter.

Reference - <https://gadgets360.com/telecom/news/reliance-jio-5g-rollout-october-dial-plans-full-coverage-2023-end-3296296>

Insta launches new collaborative collections feature to save posts shared with friends

04

Meta-owned Instagram has launched a new "collaborative collections" feature that will let users and their friends save and share images with each other. With this new feature, people can connect with friends over common interests by saving posts to a collaborative collection in their group chat or a one-on-one DM, according to TechCrunch. "Now when you go to save a piece of content on Feed or from your DMs, you'll see a new option to create a collaborative collection," Instagram head Adam Mosseri was quoted as saying.

<https://www.dailypioneer.com/2022/technology/meta-to-make-it-easier-to-switch-between-fb-instagram-accounts.html>

05

Microsoft brings ads to its Bing chat

Microsoft has announced that it is bringing ads to its AI-powered Bing chat, its new search agent powered by OpenAI's GPT-4. Yusuf Mehdi, Microsoft corporate vice president, in a blogpost said, the company is "exploring placing ads in the chat experience to share the ad revenue with partners whose content contributed to the chat response". According to the company, there are now more than 100 million daily active users of Bing. New scenarios like chat are driving engagement, including more than 100 million chats.

<https://indianexpress.com/article/technology/tech-news-technology/google-chrome-to-soon-add-fingerprint-locking-for-incognito-tabs-heres-how-it-will-work-6156967/>

06

Evolve 4.0

Evolve Global Corp, a New York-based provider of demand generation, business process outsourcing, and data migration solutions, has announced a transformative shift in its business model. This shift is driven by the company's founder and CEO, Satish K. Sadasivan, who aims to better serve the needs of society and the planet. The company, which has a strong presence in America, India, the Philippines, Dominican Republic, the UK, and more, has conducted a comprehensive review of its vision, mission, values, and market trends, which has led to this transformation, addressed as Evolve 4.0.

Evolve 4.0

https://www.gadgetsnow.com/tech-news/apple-to-launch-standalone-classical-music-app-this-year/articleshow/94587043.cms?referrer=amp_articlelist

Microsoft launches GPT-4 based Security Copilot for cyber defence

07

Tech giant Microsoft has launched its new "Security Copilot" for cyber defence which is based on Open AI's GPT-4 technology. Microsoft Security Copilot quickly detects and responds to threats and better understands the threat landscape overall, the tech giant said in a statement. "Security Copilot will combine Microsoft's vast threat intelligence footprint with industry leading expertise to augment the work of security professionals through an easy-to-use AI assistant." This new tool is currently available through private preview.

https://www.gadgetsnow.com/tech-news/eu-proposes-rules-making-it-easier-to-sue-drone-makers-ai-systems/articleshow/94515699.cms?referrer=amp_articlelist

08

Spotify introduces 'Niche Mixes' feature

Music streaming platform Spotify has introduced its new "Niche Mixes" feature which is a set of personalised playlists that combines all the Mixes offered in a playful way. To access the new feature, users can navigate to the "Made For You" hub within the Search tab to find five to 10 Mixes that the company thinks they will like, the platform said in a blogpost on Tuesday. "If you're looking to get super specific, search for an activity, vibe, or aesthetic that describes the moment you're in, and then add the word 'mix' at the end." Mixes are available for all people globally to Free and Premium users who search Spotify in English.

https://www.gadgetsnow.com/tech-news/india-seizes-bitcoin-worth-rs-12-93-crore-after-the-kolkata-gaming-app-fraud/articleshow/94515604.cms?referrer=amp_articlelist

09

WhatsApp's new update gives admins more control over who can join group

Meta CEO Mark Zuckerberg has announced two new updates for "groups" on WhatsApp -- new controls for admins, and easily see groups in common. The new features which will start rolling out globally over the coming weeks, come just a few months after WhatsApp launched Communities, a feature that offers larger, more structured discussion groups. It has built a tool that gives admins the ability to decide who is able to join a group, giving admins more control over their group privacy.

<https://indianexpress.com/article/explained/explained-sci-tech/pm-narendra-modi-to-launch-5g-tomorrow-october-1-882334/>

Pinterest to add shopping feature to its Shuffles app

10

Photo-sharing social media platform Pinterest has announced that it is working on ways to add Shuffles collage content into Pinterest, beginning with shopping. The collage-making app Shuffles will now have access to the same shopping features as regular pins. Users will be able to tap individual collage cutouts to see the brand, price, and other product metadata, as well as shop for similar products, according to TechCrunch. Shuffles are a collage tool that allows users to create, publish and share visual content.

<https://healthanalytics.com/news/harvard-stanford-develop-self-supervised-ai-to-detect-disease-via-x-ray>

11

Hindenburg report wipes out \$526 mn from Jack Dorsey's worth

Former Twitter co-founder and CEO Jack Dorsey was left poorer by \$526 million after short-seller Hindenburg Research revealed that his digital payment company Block facilitates fraud against consumers and the government. After his worst single-day decline, Dorsey is now worth \$4.4 billion, according to Bloomberg Billionaires Index. Block's shares also nosedived as much as 22 per cent on Thursday, before closing down 15 per cent late on Thursday.

<https://www.theverge.com/2022/9/27/2337502/intel-samsung-display-slidable-pc-concept>

12

Marcowagon introduces brand XINT in India

Another brand milestone has been achieved by Marcowagon, with XINT being officially launched exclusively on Ajo. Marcowagon Retail Pvt. Ltd. is a leading licensee for global fashion and lifestyle brands and has successfully launched & built Global brands through Indian e-commerce & retailing. Launched brands like NA-KD, Trendyol, Mavi (Turkey), OVS (Italy), LC Waikiki and Tom Tailor (Germany) are enjoying success with leading platforms like Ajo Reliance, Myntra, Nykaa Fashion, Amazon, Flipkart, firstcry.com, and Tata Cliq, among many others

<https://techcrunch.com/2022/09/21/apple-to-move-25-iphone-production-to-india-by-2025-20-ipad-and-apple-watch-to-vietnam/>

Ashneer Grover launches fantasy sports app CrickPe ahead of IPL

13

Ahead of the Indian Premier League (IPL) 2023 that begins from March 31, Ashneer Grover's new venture Third Unicorn has launched a fantasy sports app called CrickPe that aims to take on Dream11 and Mobile Premier League (MPL). CrickPe will levy a 10 per cent platform fee of the total funds received for any public or private contest. It allows players above 18 years of age to create a virtual team of cricket players and enter paid contests to earn cash prizes.

<https://www.outlookindia.com/business/what-is-moonlighting-here-s-why-wipro-fired-300-employees-for-doing-it-news-225205>

14

Epic Games launches Unreal Editor for Fortnite, Creator Economy 2.0

At the 2023 edition of the Game Developers Conference (GDC) in the US, video game developer Epic Games has announced some of its new technological capabilities, including -- Unreal Editor for Fortnite, Creator Economy 2.0, and more. Unreal Editor for Fortnite (UEFN), launched in Public Beta for creators and developers is a version of "Unreal Editor" that can create and publish experiences directly to Fortnite. The company also launched MetaHuman Animator -- a new feature set for the MetaHuman framework, which will enable users to reproduce any facial performance as high-fidelity animation on MetaHuman characters.

<https://indiaexpress.com/article/technology/science/researchers-use-4g-5g-robot-learning-to-learn-to-improve-human-robot-conversations-8161917#:~:text=Researchers%20at%20the%20University%20of%20Cincinnati,with%20the%20use%20of%20artificial%20intelligence,Facebook%20to%20robotic%20chatbots%20AI>

15

Mozilla introduces new startup to build open, trustworthy AI

The company said that it is initially investing \$30 million to build this new startup. "The vision for Mozilla.ai is to make it easy to develop trustworthy AI products. We will build things and hire/collaborate with people that share our vision: AI that has agency, accountability, transparency and openness at its core. Mozilla.ai will be a space outside big tech and academia for like-minded founders, developers, scientists, product managers and builders to gather," Mark Surman, the executive president of Mozilla and the head of Mozilla.ai, said in a blogpost. Mozilla purchased the startup as it builds out Hubs, the company's virtual reality (VR) collaboration platform.

<https://www.engadget.com/snapchat-for-web-is-now-available-for-everyone-130052210.html>

Unknown Facts

The Internet Hit 5.1 Billion Users in 2023.

60% Of Internet Use Is Mobile.

There Were 3 Zettabytes of Internet Traffic in 2020.

Social Media Platforms Dominate Among Internet Users.

More Than 50% Of Internet Users Make E-commerce Purchases Weekly.

DID YOU KNOW?

News of the Month

PM Modi unveils 6G test bed, industry hails move

After a successful 5G rollout in the country, Prime Minister Narendra Modi on Wednesday announced the Bharat 6G vision document and launched the 6G research and development (R&D) test bed.

Inaugurating the new International Telecommunication Union (ITU) area office and innovation centre during a programme at Vigyan Bhawan here, he said that the 6G R&D test bed will help faster adoption of the new technology in the country. The government said that the Bharat 6G vision document and 6G test bed will provide an enabling environment for innovation, capacity building, and faster technology adoption in the country.

The industry hailed the PM's move to roll out the 6G test bed in the country. "6G holds the possibility to provide extreme speeds with predictably low latency and a low jitter rate for high demanding scenarios and about 10Cr active 6G devices by 2030," said Arvind Bali, CEO, Telecom Sector Skill Council (TSSC). "By providing a platform for academic research, industry, and startups, the 6G Test Bed can pave the way for the development of skilled and innovative workforce," he added. In August last year, PM Modi had said that the government is preparing to launch 6G by the end of this decade.

Top Websites to Find Remote Jobs

www.weworkremotely.com

www.virtualvocations.com

www.workingnomads.com

www.freshersworld.com

www.remoteok.com

www.justremote.co

www.flexjobs.com

www.crossover.com

www.simplyhired.com

www.angel.co

www.toggl.com

www.remote.co

www.dice.com

The Artificial Intelligence Month

March 3

- OpenAI released ChatGPT and Whisper APIs

March 10

- Discord launched AI features
- Microsoft's New AI-integrated Bing crossed 100 mn Daily Active Users

March 30

- Spline unveiled Spline 3D - ChatGPT for 3D designers

March 29

- ChatGPT alternative Perplexity released new iPhone app

March 28

- Apple aquired an AI startup WaveOne
- Zoom released ZoomIQ

March 17

- GPT-4 officially launched by Open AI
- Google brings AI-integrated Workspace
- Microsoft launched 365 Copilot

March 22

- Bing launched Bing image creator
- Google revealed Bard to the public
- Adobe launched Firefly - an AI image editor
- Opera released in-browser AI tools

March 21

- AI model created to predict Cancer patient survival rate
- Runway released video generating AI Gen-2

March 24

- ChatGPT released Plugin - the app store to ChatGPT
- Canva launched new AI tools

March 27

- Stanford student create RizzGPT - it listen real - time conversations and guides you what to say next

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Ayan Arif (B.C.A. 3rd year)
(Editor)

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06 IIT Guwahati researchers develop low-cost materials for spectroscopic detection of trace chemicals

Researchers at the Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Guwahati have developed a new form of a semiconductor that can be used to identify trace chemicals using a technique called Surface Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS). Spectroscopy is a technique that analyses the interactions between light and matter to identify and characterise many types of chemicals and molecules. SERS is useful for the detection of trace amounts of chemicals in various situations like pollutants in water and biomarkers in blood.

<https://www.gadgetsnow.com/tech-news/apple-to-launch-standalone-traceable-music-app-this-year/articleshow/9650703.cms?referral=amp-articleslist>

07 IISc researchers design tiny supercapacitor capable of storing large amount of electric charge

Researchers at the Indian Institute of Science (IISc) have designed a novel, tiny device capable of storing an enormous amount of electric charge. The ultra-micro supercapacitor is also much smaller and more compact than existing supercapacitors and can potentially be used in many devices ranging from streetlights to consumer electronics, electric cars and medical devices, according to Bengaluru-based IISc. Most of these devices are currently powered by batteries.

<https://www.gadgetsnow.com/tech-news/iisr-proposes-nano-making-it-easier-to-charge-drivers-of-systems/articleshow/9430559.cms?referral=amp-articleslist>

08 Australia bans TikTok from federal government devices

Australia has become the last of the “Five Eyes” security partners to ban the Chinese-owned video-sharing app TikTok from its federal government’s devices. Attorney-General Mark Dreyfus said in a statement Tuesday that based on intelligence and security agencies’ advice, that ban would come into effect “as soon as practicable.” The so-called Five Eyes intelligence-sharing partners -- the United States, Canada, Britain and New Zealand -- have taken similar steps.

<https://www.gadgetsnow.com/tech-news/india-seizes-bitcoin-worth-rs-42-lakhs-crore-after-the-kolkata-gaming-app-fraud/articleshow/9455804.cms?referral=amp-articleslist>

09 India among top three markets for AI-powered Bing preview: Microsoft official

India has emerged as one of the top three markets for Microsoft’s new Bing preview, which has ChatGPT incorporated into it, and is its biggest image creator market, a senior company official has said, asserting that the search engine is much better than its rival Google. Powered by ChatGPT, Microsoft launched the new Bing preview on February 7. ChatGPT is an artificial intelligence chatbot developed by OpenAI and launched in November 2022.

<https://indianexpress.com/article/technology/artificial-intelligence/microsoft-launches-bing-preview-tomorrow-october-11-892334/>

10 Samsung cutting memory chip production as profit slides

Samsung Electronics said Friday it’s cutting the production of its computer memory chips in an apparent effort to reduce inventory as it forecasted another quarter of sluggish profit. The South Korean technology giant in a regulatory filing said it has been reducing the production of certain memory products by unspecified “meaningful levels” to optimize its manufacturing operations, adding it has sufficient supplies of those chips to meet demand fluctuations.

<https://businessanalytics.com/news/industry-standard-develop-seid-supervised-ai-to-detect-disease-14-11-2023>

11 Scientists develop eco-friendly 3D printed polymer parts from terrestrial insects

An international team, including researchers from India, has successfully developed a method of using a compound from terrestrial insects to manufacture eco-friendly polymer composite parts with the 3D printing method. The researchers, including those from Sri Ramakrishna Engineering College in Tamil Nadu, used Chitosan derived from chitin, a compound found in the exoskeletons of arthropods such as insects, as well as in sea creatures such as the shells of crabs.

<https://www.theverge.com/2022/9/12/23175029/samsung-dkplay-slide-the-pc-concept>

12 Experience the Next Level of Virtual Interaction with MyWaha's Immersive Media Platform

MyWaha is a short video content platform that allows users to create and share short videos with their followers. With video content becoming increasingly popular, it is more important than ever to have a strong online presence. MyWaha provides the perfect platform to do just that, allowing users to manage, distribute, and interact with any content quickly and easily. One of the standout features of MyWaha is its full-funnel approach and multi-objective media strategy, offering users a wholesome new virtual experience.

<https://techcrunch.com/2022/09/21/apple-to-move-25-iphone-production-to-india-by-2025-26-pod-and-apple-watch-to-vietnam/>

ChatGPT: how to use AI as a virtual financial adviser

13

AI tools might seem overly complex or expensive to non-experts, but advances in natural language processing and machine learning could turn ChatGPT and similar products into virtual personal finance assistants. This would mean having an expert on hand to help you make sense of the latest financial news and data. Researchers have started to explore the potential of AI tools like ChatGPT, but given how new this technology is, much of the academic research remains in the early stages.

<https://www.outlookindia.com/business/What-is-moonlighting-heres-why-its-pro-fired-300-employees-for-doing-it-news-225205>

14 Log9 commissions country's first commercial Li-ion cell manufacturing line

Battery technology start up Log9 Materials on Friday inaugurated the country's first lithium-ion cell manufacturing facility in Bengaluru. The company launched the commercial Li-ion cell production facility at its campus in Jakkur, Bengaluru. The plant has an initial capacity of 50 MWh. Log9 materials has also launched its indigenously developed battery management system (BMS) incorporated with power control mechanisms and SoX algorithms to ensure high safety and reliability for high-power applications.

Power. Performance. Peace of Mind.

<https://business.bbc.com/news/technology-62828282>

15 Third Eye Production Company Emerges as a Top Creative Agency for High-Quality Ads and Videos

The Third Eye Production Company is a leading creative agency that specializes in producing high-quality ads and videos for businesses of all sizes. Founded recently, the company has made a name for itself by delivering exceptional visual content that resonates with audiences. At The Third Eye, the team of experts works with a wide range of clients, including large corporations, small businesses, and start-ups, to develop and produce visually compelling content that engages and informs.

<https://www.engadget.com/what-chat-for-web-is-now-available-for-everyone-0303220.html>

Unknown Facts

- 90% of the world's data was created in the last two years.
- The global artificial intelligence (AI) market is expected to reach \$126 billion by 2025.
- The world's first electronic computer, the Colossus, was built in 1943.
- The first webcam was invented at the University of Cambridge to monitor the coffee pot in the computer science department.
- The first computer game, "Spacewar!", was invented in 1962.

DID YOU KNOW?

News of the Month

First stores in India Mark Company's major expansion in country: Apple

As it celebrates more than 25 years in India, iPhone-maker Apple on Monday, 17 April 2023 said its first two stores in the country to be opened this week mark a major expansion plan of the company. India's first Apple Store opened in Mumbai on April 18, 2023, a flagship retail outlet at the Jio World Centre in BKC. A second Apple Store opened in New Delhi's Saket, on April 20. Two Apple Stores in two days is unprecedented in several ways, and underlines the importance of India as a market for Apple. Both the stores have been designed to resonate with local look and feel, Apple said. "India has such a beautiful culture and an incredible energy, and we are excited to build on our long-standing history — supporting our customers, investing in local communities, and working together to build a better future with innovations that serve humanity," Apple CEO Tim Cook said. Apple exports from India are estimated to have crossed USD 5 billion in the financial year 2022-23 which is about half of the total exports of "Made In India" phones. The company started manufacturing iPhones in India in 2017 through its contract manufacturers. "Apple's work with Indian suppliers of all sizes supports hundreds of thousands of jobs across the country," the statement said.

The company also said that it works one-on-one with developers to help take their apps from "good to great" at the iOS App Design and Development Accelerator in Bengaluru. "India's vibrant community of app developers now supports more than 1 million jobs. A testament to the tremendous growth of developers in India, App Store pay-outs to developers in the country have more than tripled since 2018," the statement added.

Networking Protocols

FTP

File Transfer Protocol Port 21

SSH

Secure Shell Port 22

SFTP

Secure File Transfer Protocol

SMTP

Simple Mail Transfer Protocol Port 25

DNS

Domain Naming System (01 Service) : Port 53

HTTP

Hypertext Transfer Protocol - Port 80

POP3

Post Office Protocol - Port 110

IMAP

Internet Message Access Protocol - Port 143

HTTPS

HTTP Secure - Port 443

RDP

Remote Desktop Protocol Port 3389

TCP

Transmission Control Protocol

UDP

User Datagram Protocol

ARP

Address Resolution Protocol

RARP

Reverse ARP

DHCP

Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol

MTP

Media Transfer Protocol

Programming Language You Should Learn To Become

DATA ANALYSIS

DESKTOP DEVELOPER

EMBEDED SYSTEM PROGRAM

WEB DEVELOPER

MOBILE APP DEVELOPER

GAME DEVELOPER

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01

United Arab Emirates is heading for the asteroid belt

The spacecraft, named MBR Explorer after Sheikh Mohammed bin Rashid al-Maktoum, the ruler of Dubai and prime minister of the UAE, is scheduled to launch in 2028. Building off the success of its Hope spacecraft, which is still circling and studying Mars, the United Arab Emirates announced plans for an ambitious follow-up mission: a grand tour of the asteroid belt. In February 2030, the spacecraft will arrive at Westerwald, a 1.4-mile-wide asteroid, zipping past at 20,000 mph on its way to visit six more objects in the asteroid belt between Mars and Jupiter. The UAE is a newcomer to spaceflight.

https://www.gadgetsnow.com/tech-news/apple-ceo-tim-cook-hits-europe-for-a-full-fledged-tour-key-details/articleshow/94512633.cms?referrer=amp_articlelist

02

EU tech chief calls for voluntary AI code of conduct within months

EU industry chief Thierry Breton said last week that Alphabet and the European Commission aimed to develop an AI pact as concerns mount about the impact on society particularly from generative AI. The European Union's AI Act, with rules on facial recognition and biometric surveillance, could be the world's first comprehensive legislation governing the technology, but is still going through the legislative process. Leaders of the G7 nations called earlier this month for the development of technical standards to keep AI "trustworthy", urging international discussions on topics such as governance, copyrights, transparency and the threat of disinformation.

<https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/tech/information-tech/tcs-poised-to-seal-likely-2-billion-deal-for-bsnl-4g/articleshow/94542008.cms>

03

Govt to examine WhatsApp's breach of privacy: Minister

The government will investigate a claim that WhatsApp accessed the microphone of smartphone users while the phone was not in use, Minister of State for Electronics and Information Technology Rajeev Chandrasekhar said. In a tweet, the minister said the government will examine the alleged breach of privacy even as the new Digital Personal Data Protection Bill was being readied. This followed a claim that WhatsApp accessed a user's microphone while he was sleeping.

Reference - <https://gadgets360.com/telecom/news/reliance-jio-5g-rollout-october-dial-plans-full-coverage-2023-end-3296296>

Computex 2023: All the major announcements

04

COMPUTEX
TAIPEI

Computex is finally back to its in-person format after three long years. Taking place in Taipei, Taiwan, Computex 2023 is the event to follow to get all the updates related to the latest PC world and innovations from renowned brands. This year's Computex goes beyond hardware and will showcase software, services, and, of course, the ever-evolving field of artificial intelligence-powered products and services.

05

Govt has used technology as source of empowerment, to ensure social justice: PM Modi

Be it JAM trinity, CoWIN portal or digital market for farmers, his government has used technology as an "agent of inclusion", he said, adding that there is some technological solution available at every stage of life right from one's birth. The prime minister said his government's thrust on science and technology has ushered in a big change and noted that around 4,000 patents used to be registered annually 10 years back but it is over 30,000 now.

<https://indianexpress.com/article/technology/tech-news-technology/google-chrome-to-soon-add-fingerprint-locking-for-incognito-tabs-heres-how-it-will-work-9156967/>

06

RailTel and NuRe Bharat Unveil All-in-One Railway App

3i Infotech-led consortium NuRe Bharat Network and RailTel on 16 May 2023 unveiled PIPOnet mobile app which aims to provide all services, including e-ticketing, travel, stay reservations, and entertainment apps, for railway passengers. NuRe Bharat Network CEO Sax Krishna said that the app will become available on Android Play Store in the next two weeks. He said that PIPOnet will allow the advertisers to connect deeply with the people of Bharat across Tier 1,2,3 and 4 towns of India.

https://www.gadgetsnow.com/tech-news/apple-to-launch-standalone-classical-music-app-this-year/articleshow/94587043.cms?referrer=amp_articlelist

09

AI means everyone can now be a programmer, Nvidia chief says

Nvidia has surged to become the world's most valuable listed semiconductor company as a major supplier of chips and computing systems for artificial intelligence. Nvidia has surged to become the world's most valuable listed semiconductor company as a major supplier of chips and computing systems for artificial intelligence. The company last week forecast second-quarter revenue more than 50% above Wall Street estimates and said it was boosting supply to meet surging demand for its artificial-intelligence chips, which are used to power ChatGPT and many similar services.

<https://indianexpress.com/article/explained/explained-sci-tech/pm-narendra-modi-to-launch-5g-tomorrow-october-1-882334/>

Coding for a cause: 20-yr-old Asmi Jain from Indore wins WDC23 challenge with health app

07

For 20-year-old Medi-Caps University student Asmi Jain, coding is more than just a skill – it's a way of making a difference. When she learned that her friend's uncle had suffered from eye misalignment and facial paralysis after brain surgery, she decided to use her programming talent to create a solution. Her innovative playground app, using the Swift coding language, uses eye-tracking technology to help users exercise their eye muscles and improve coordination by following a moving ball on the screen.

https://www.gadgetsnow.com/tech-news/eu-proposes-rules-making-it-easier-to-sue-drone-makers-ai-systems/articleshow/94595699.cms?referrer=amp_articlelist

Microsoft partners with British Council to develop English skills of 400,000 young Indians

10

The 'English Skills for Youth' solution will be integrated into rural engineering colleges. British Council and Microsoft India have entered into a three-year partnership programme called 'English Skills for Youth' aimed at empowering young people, particularly women, in socio-economically disadvantaged communities across India. The Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) signed between the two organisations highlights the objective of enhancing employability opportunities for youth aged 18-25.

<https://healthitanalytics.com/news/harvard-stanford-develop-self-supervised-ai-to-detect-disease-via-x-ray>

08

A camera without lens ? Paragraphica generates images using location data & AI

Introducing Paragraphica, the world's first context-to-image camera that visualises a photo based on location data and AI. The camera comes as a physical unit and a virtual camera that users can try. According to the official website, the camera works by collecting location data with the help of open APIs (application programming interfaces). It uses information such as time of the day, address, weather, and places in the vicinity. Paragraphica writes a paragraph based on the combination of all these details.

https://www.gadgetsnow.com/tech-news/ed-sizes-bitcoin-worth-rs-12-83-crore-after-the-kolkata-gaming-app-fraud/articleshow/94595604.cms?referrer=amp_articlelist

11

From green blood to limited playtime: A look at the new features on BGMI

With its second comeback to India, the studio has made several changes to BGMI in compliance with the Government of India. Much to the joy of mobile gamers, Krafton's BGMI (Battlegrounds Mobile India) version 2.5 is finally available for both Android and iOS devices. BGMI is reported to have over 100 million active players and has clocked over 130 million downloads on the Google Play Store. With its second comeback to India, the studio has made several changes in compliance with the Government of India.

<https://www.theverge.com/2022/9/27/2337502/intel-samsung-display-slidable-pc-concept>

News of the Month

Digital technology in education sector

The Covid pandemic has made this process much faster, relevant and robust. By deploying remote learning technologies through a combination of TV, radio, online and mobile platforms, a large number of institutions were able to cater to the educational needs of their students. The G20 Education Working Group Meeting on 'The Role of Digital Technologies in Education' comes as a key development in this regard, highlighting a slew of present and prospective technological measures. Identification of core areas and themes to promote possible research and academic collaboration among educational institutions in G20 member countries, is a huge development, as the group comprises some of the most developed countries of the world, who use world-class research, innovation and cutting-edge technologies in this domain. The selection of priority areas for deliberations such as 'Foundational Literacy and Numeracy', 'Tech-enabled learning', 'Future of work' and 'Research and innovation collaboration', - broad-based discussions with enriching inputs from sectoral experts.

Hence, the union budget 2023 emphasises much on digitisation of education. The Digital India programme has received Rs 4,795.24 crore, and to boost digital infrastructure, the government has proposed initiatives like Digital Libraries and Digital Universities. States have also been urged to set up physical libraries at panchayat levels to provide infrastructure for accessing the National Digital Library resources. Digital initiatives with a focus on artificial intelligence terming it a step towards the 'digital revolution', have been hailed by all. Three centres of excellence for AI and 100 laboratories in engineering institutions for developing applications using 5G services, will only add to this process of digital revolution. Digital Universities aim to reach out to the remotest regions of the country with quality, skill-based and job-oriented courses and training.

World's Password Day

Password Management Mistakes to Avoid

Not using multi-factor authentication:

Use this feature wherever possible, it prevents 99.9% data breaches

Storing passwords in plaintext:

Never store your password in a note on your phone or written on a sticky note. Use a password manager instead.

Not changing your password after a data breach:

Change your password immediately upon learning of a compromised account.

Prioritizing convenience over security:

Don't focus on what's easiest to remember or what's the least hassle when creating a password, your security depends on it.

Reusing passwords: Even if you have a strong and complex password, create a unique password for every account.

National Technology Day

National Technology Day is celebrated in India on May 11 every year to commemorate the historic nuclear test carried out by India on May 11, 1998, in Pokhran, Rajasthan. The successful testing of the nuclear bomb, code-named Operation Shakti, made India the sixth country in the world to possess nuclear technology. Former Prime Minister Atal Bihari Vajpayee first declared May 11 as National Technology Day in 1999 to honour Indian scientists, engineers, and technologists.

Important Facts

There are more than 3.8 billion Social media users on the planet.

Free domains were available until 1995.

Radio took 38 years to achieve 50 million people, whilst the web only took four years.

The Mouse was originally known as the X-Y Position Indicator in the 1960s.

Robots will be used to perform the majority of the tedious and unneeded tasks in the future. In Czech, the word “robot” literally implies “forced labour.”

Technophobia is a dread of technology that certain individuals have, much like any other phobia.

Email existed long before the WorldWideWeb, often known as the Internet. Ray Tomlinson invented the former in the 1960s, while the latter was founded in the late 1980s.

According to 2019 data, you spend an average of ten years of your life watching television. With Netflix, Prime Videos, and a slew of other video streaming applications, usage may skyrocket.

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WELCOME TO DIGITAL AND TECHNICAL WORLD

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01

Apple's new \$3k 'face computer'

The headset, named Apple Vision Pro, has been in the works for years, with Apple taking its familiar wait-and-see approach while other giant tech companies have dived headfirst into the still-kludgy AR/VR market. The new platform and headset have massive implications for the rest of the market; once Apple wades into a product category, it often both validates the category and obviates competitors.

02

Billions of devices will be trading with each other by 2030

By the end of the decade, some 3.3 billion Internet-connected devices (IoT devices) will be trading money and data directly, a new report from telecommunications consultants STL Partners claims.

That's up from 88 million devices next year, representing a 3750% increase in roughly six years, or "meteoric growth", as the report's authors put it. The practice is being dubbed the Economy of Things (EoT). This subset of IoT, the researchers claim, will

03

Nvidia brings its AI computing platform to cloud data firm Snowflake

Snowflake a cloud data analytics company, is partnering with computing company Nvidia to allow customers ranging from financial institutions to healthcare and retail to build AI models using their own data. The two companies announced the partnership at Snowflake Summit 2023 on 26/06/2023. Sloodman said companies that use Snowflake to manage their data will be able to now use their own data to train new AI models to gain an advantage in business without risking losing control of it.

Google will now pay you some serious dough to find security flaws in Chrome

Google has announced plans to triple the amount of cash available to those submitting their findings to its Vulnerability Reward Program (VRP) for Chrome in certain circumstances, with pots of up to \$180,000 available until the start of December 2023.

Google offers \$180,000 to find Chrome bugs.

04

05

Four Indian firms in WEF's 100 most promising tech startup list

The World Economic Forum (WEF) named four Indian entities, including Giftalexia Solutions and Xacmaz Technology, in its annual list of 100 most promising technology pioneers, comprising companies making progress in sustainability, advanced manufacturing and inclusive healthcare. The other two Indian entities on the list are evolutionQ, which offers quantum-safe cybersecurity products and Next Big Innovation Labs -- which is developing customisable 3D bioprinter to bridge the gap between organ demand and availability via 3D bioengineered organs.

06

Zoom will now use AI to sum up that meeting you missed

Zoom has started rolling out Zoom IQ with the first features now available for select users to try. The company describes Zoom IQ as a “smart companion” that is powered by generative AI.

Zoom IQ will be able to generate meeting summaries and compose chats, with the company promising an additional five features “soon” and likely even more in the coming months and years.

09

ICC World Cup 2023 Trophy Becomes One Of First Official Sporting Trophies To Send To Space

The 2023 ODI World Cup trophy was launched on a stratospheric scale, one lakh 20 thousand feet above the earth before making a spectacular landing at world's largest cricket stadium in Ahmedabad. The trophy was attached to a bespoke stratospheric balloon to be launched into space, giving fans in various countries a chance to connect with the trophy.

Union minister Ashwini Vaishnaw demonstrates the semiconductor tech Micron is set to bring to India

07

US memory chip giant Micron Technology Inc recently announced that it would invest up to \$825 million in a new chip assembly and test facility in India. The plant will be the company's first factory in India and will be set up in the state of Gujarat. Announcing the new chip facility, Micron said that with support from the central as well as the government of Gujarat, the total investment in the

YouTube content creators will soon be able to dub videos in other languages for free

10

YouTube is getting a new feature which will help creators dub videos in other languages. On Thursday at VidCon 2023, the online video-sharing platform announced that it will be using Aloud, a product from Google's in-house Area 120 incubator. Until now, content creators had to rely on third-party apps or providers if they wanted to make videos in different languages. Last year, Google introduced Aloud, an AI-powered dubbing product that can automatically transcribe a video and produce a dubbed version of the same. It also offers the option to review and edit the transcription before generating the dub.

08

Alphabet bets on lasers to deliver internet in remote areas

The project known as Taara is part of Alphabet's innovation lab called X, also nicknamed the “Moonshot Factory.” It was initiated in 2016 after attempts at using stratospheric balloons to deliver internet ran into problems due to high costs, company executives said. Taara executives and Bharti Airtel, one of India's largest telecommunications and internet

11

Punjab National Bank launches IVR-based UPI solution

UPI123 Pay is an instant payment solution for feature phone (non-smartphone) users who can use Unified Payments Interface (UPI) payment service in a fast and easy manner; it allows users to make payments without using the internet. Punjab National Bank (PNB) becomes the first public sector bank to introduce an IVR-based UPI solution - UPI 123PAY, aligning with the Digital Payment Vision 2025 towards a cashless and cardless

12 Apple planning to launch credit card in India in partnership with HDFC Bank

Toyota Motor will launch high-performance solid-state batteries for electric vehicles (EVs) from 2026 and aims to commercialize its mass-production by 2027-2028 while developing technologies to reduce the cost of EVs and batteries. Toyota aims to produce about 1.7 million vehicles by 2030, half of its 3.5 million EV target by that year, and to sell a new EV with a lithium-ion battery that offers a range of 1,000 km.

IIT Madras Researchers Develop Data Science, IoT-Based Method for Mobile Pollution Monitoring

Researchers IIT Madras have made significant progress in the field of air pollution monitoring by developing a low-cost mobile air pollution monitoring framework. This innovative approach utilizes data science, Internet of Things (IoT) technology, and low-cost pollution sensors mounted on public vehicles to dynamically monitor air quality at a high spatial and temporal resolution. The project, known as Kaatru (meaning “air” in Tamil), aims to address the limitations of traditional stationary monitoring stations and provide valuable insights for policy-making and mitigation strategies

13

14 Microsoft joins Indian govt to train 6K students, 200 educators in cybersecurity skills

Microsoft has signed a memorandum of understanding (MoU) with Directorate General of Training (DGT) under the Ministry of Skills Development and Entrepreneurship (MSDE) to train 6,000 students and 200 educators in digital and cyber-security skills in the country. As part of this collaboration with, Microsoft will offer a wide range of courses, including training in AI, cloud computing, web development and cybersecurity skills for students and 200 faculty members at government-led Industrial Training Institutes (ITIs) and National Skills Training Institutions (NSTIs).

15

AI Supercomputer ‘AIRAWAT’ puts India among top supercomputing league

The International Supercomputing Conference (ISC 2023) in Germany, the AI Supercomputer ‘AIRAWAT’, situated at C-DAC, Pune, achieved an impressive global ranking of 75th on the esteemed Top 500 Global Supercomputing List. This accomplishment establishes India as a leading nation in the field of AI supercomputing. ‘AIRAWAT’ is part of the Government of India’s National Program on AI and represents a significant stride forward in the country’s AI capabilities.

Unknown Facts

Samsung is 38 years and 1 month older than apple.

The radio took 38 years to reach an audience of 50 million.

Over 6000 new computer viruses are created and released every month.

Apollo 11 astronauts couldn't afford insurance.

Did You Know

News of the Month

IIT-K conducts artificial rain test through cloud seeding

The Indian Institute of Technology-Kanpur (IIT-K) successfully conducted a test for artificial rain via cloud-seeding over a limited area on the sprawling campus. On 21/06/2023, a plane flew to a height of 5,000ft from the institute's airstrip, firing powder spray amid thick clouds, which resulted in heavy rain. The project, initiated by IIT Kanpur in 2017, faced multiple hurdles, including delays in obtaining necessary permissions. However, after meticulous preparations and thorough evaluations, the Directorate of Civil Aviation (DGCA) finally granted permission for the test flight. During the test, a Cessna aircraft took flight from IIT Kanpur's airstrip, reaching an altitude of 5000 feet.

Using cloud seeding technology, the aircraft released chemical powder into the clouds, stimulating the formation of raindrops. Shortly after, rainfall was observed in the surrounding areas, validating the effectiveness of the artificial rain technique. This breakthrough in cloud seeding technology holds promising prospects for regions such as Bundelkhand in Uttar Pradesh, which have long suffered from drought. By creating artificial clouds and inducing rainfall, this technique has the potential to bring significant relief to drought-stricken areas.

7 Steps Of DATA SCIENTIST

Understand role and responsibilities of Data Scientist

Improve mathematical, Programming, Technical & Business Strategically Skills

Use Big Data Software Like Hadoop, Spark to Achieve Distributed Processing

Working With DBMS Will Surely Go A Long Way In Securing Your Dream job.

Be Master Of Data Munging, Visualisation and Reporting and Expert to Convert Raw Data into Easy to Study and Analysis Form

Learn Code - Be a good programmer within the language in which data communicate

Lastly you need to stay up-to-date with the Data Scientist Community

International Women In Engineering Day

INTERNATIONAL
WOMEN
IN ENGINEERING DAY
JUNE 23

International Women in Engineering Day is celebrated on June 23 every year around the world, to honor women in the field of engineering. It focuses on raising the profile of women who are changing the field of engineering one degree at a time. It has been recognized by UNESCO and is a befitting tribute for the anniversary of the Women's Engineering Society (WES), which was established on June 23, 1919.

Women Inventors

- Space rocket propulsion system • Inventor: Yvonne Brill
- Space station batteries • Inventor: Olga Gonzalez-Sanabria
- Laser cataract surgery • Inventor: Patricia Bath
- Computer software • Inventor: Grace Murray Hopper
- System to reduce noise by trains • Inventor: Mary Walton
- Electric refrigerator • Inventor: Florence Parpart
- Wireless transmission technology • Inventor: Hedy Lamarr

WOMEN IN ENGINEERING DAY TIMELINE

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DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTER APPLICATION
TECHNICAL COMMITTEE

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JULY - 2023

MONTHLY
Tech Dose

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WELCOME TO DIGITAL AND TECHNICAL WORLD

01 OpenAI CEO Sam Altman's Worldcoin Crypto Under European Regulators Scrutiny

Less than a week after its launch, the Worldcoin crypto project of OpenAI chief executive Sam Altman is already under scrutiny by European regulators over its reliance on an eye scan to verify a user's identity, France's data protection agency said Friday.

Worldcoin's launch on Monday comes as the cryptocurrency industry is suffering hard times after the spectacular collapse of FTX and various legal cases against the sector's biggest players.

Using eye scans, it tries to solve one of the main challenges facing the crypto industry: a level of anonymity so high that makes it vulnerable to scams and spam bots -- which AI threatens to make exponentially worse.

02 British Museum Step into Metaverse, Partners With The Sandbox

The British Museum, based in London, is ready to step into the world of metaverse. The home of Britain's history since the mid-eighteenth century will now have an address in The Sandbox, a platform that provides a fully functional virtual universe that lets entities exist as avatars. The entry of this historic British landmark into the metaverse is just another testification to UK's open-mindedness about Web3. The UK, in recent months, has shown a steadfast approach towards embracing the up-and-coming Web3 sector that encompasses projects related to crypto, NFTs, and the metaverse.

As part of this collaboration, NFTs inspired by some artifacts showcased in the museum will be launched for collectors to own as a piece of history in detailed digital versions.

03 Countdown to NASA's Streaming Service !

NASA is getting in on the "+" streaming action. The government agency announced that it's going to launch a new streaming service later this year called NASA+. The ad-free, no-cost streaming service will include live coverage of future launches, documentaries and new original series that will be exclusively available on the platform.

"We're putting space on demand and at your fingertips with NASA's new streaming platform," said Marc Etkind, NASA's associate administrator of communications.

From Twitter to 'X' : Elon Musk's Logo Shake-Up !

Twitter owner Elon Musk officially changed the company's famous bird logo to an "X" on Monday as part of a sweeping rebrand he announced on the social media site over the weekend.

Musk, who acquired the platform for \$44 billion late last year, wrote in a post Sunday that the company would soon "bid adieu to the twitter brand and, gradually, all the birds."

05 Microsoft 365 Copilot : Are You Ready for Your Personal AI

Microsoft last week announced the upcoming availability of Microsoft 365 Copilot, and it looks to be a huge game-changer. At the enterprise level, it will help you find anything you need inside or outside the company, and it will eventually come to learn things about you and your company that will allow it to do much of your email, typing, presentation preparation, and make you look better in front of your boss and peers. It is in an early stage, though, and just a shadow of what it will evolve into.

06 First US Robotic Liver Transplant : A Medical Milestone

A surgical team from Washington University School of Medicine in St. Louis achieved a remarkable milestone by performing the first-ever robotic liver transplant in the United States. This groundbreaking procedure, carried out at Barnes-Jewish Hospital, brings the advantages of minimally invasive robotic surgery to liver transplants, offering promising benefits for future patients in need of this life-saving procedure.

AI : The Catalysts for New-Era Cyber Crime

Cyber criminals have developed new methods to scam people by leveraging Artificial Intelligence (AI) to create convincing voice imitations of family members or friends, said Deputy Superintendent of Police, Criminal Investigation Unit, CID, Lingaraj.

07

09 UNESCO Calls for Global Ban on Smartphones in Schools

UNESCO believes smartphones should be banned from schools, as they distract students and don't really contribute to the learning process.

The UN's educational organization has launched a global new report on technology in education, calling for governments around the world to regulate its use.

Google and Bing Ads Hijacked for Malware Spread

New research by cybersecurity experts from Sophos reveals that the Google and Bing advertising networks have become channels for delivering malware to targeted users. The recently discovered malware campaign, named Nitrogen, exploits these ad networks to promote popular tools like AnyDesk. However, when unsuspecting users click on the ads, they are not directed to the legitimate websites of these products. Instead, they are redirected to compromised WordPress websites, putting them at risk of potential security threats.

10

08 This dangerous Malware Spoofs top Android apps to infect your device - here's how to safe

Cybersecurity researchers from CloudSEK uncovered a variant known as DogeRAT (Remote Access Trojan). The malware has all sorts of capabilities, from accessing contacts and messages to exfiltrating banking credentials. It can also take over the compromised device, send spam, make payments, tweak files, and even use the device's camera.

To stay safe, CloudSEK reminds, users should always be mindful about the applications they're downloading, and just because something's on the Play Store, doesn't necessarily mean it's clean and legitimate. Threat actors often manage to infiltrate Google's app repository, and sometimes add to the malware's

11

ISRO to Launch PSLV-C56 with 6 satellites

ISRO has announced the launch of PSLV-C56, scheduled for July 30th at 6:30 AM from Sriharikota's Satish Dhawan Space Centre. The mission will carry Singapore's DS-SAR satellite, featuring a Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) payload developed by Israel Aerospace Industries (IAI). This advanced SAR technology enables all-weather, day and night imaging at 1m-resolution with full polarimetry.

The DS-SAR satellite will cater to the satellite imagery requirements of various Singaporean government agencies, while ST Engineering will leverage it to offer responsive imagery and geospatial services to commercial customers.

12 HCL Tech Joins XR Startup Programme with Meity and Meta

HCL Tech, a multinational IT company, has joined the XR Startup Program, a collaborative effort between Meta and the MeitY Startup Hub, to bolster and accelerate extended reality (XR) technology startups in India.

As part of this collaboration, HCL Tech will play a key role in establishing a flourishing ecosystem for Indian startups, enabling them to lead and innovate in vital sectors like education, healthcare, and agri-tech.

SaaS Startup Plus91Labs acquires Pixely

13

Plus91Labs, a cloud consulting and IT service provider in India, has acquired Pixely (Internet X Pte Ltd), a company specialising in customised solutions for the Southeast Asian market. The acquisition of Pixely enhances Plus91Labs' existing product and service offerings, benefiting customers across various industries. Pixely's expertise in the financial services industry, fintech, NGOs, and education sectors will enable Plus91Labs to deliver tailored Salesforce solutions that address specific needs and challenges faced by organisations in these sectors.

14 India's Data Privacy Bill approved by Union Cabinet

The Union Cabinet on Wednesday approved the Digital Personal Data Protection Bill. The Bill will be taken to Parliament in the upcoming Monsoon Session to be passed as a law and once passed, it will be India's first law on data privacy and data protection.

The Bill entails penalising private as well as government entities ₹250 crore per instance in case of a data breach, which can be raised to ₹500 crores by the Data Protection Board that will be constituted as the appellate body under the law, as reported by Mint. The penalties will be decided on a case-to-case basis, depending on the severity, the scale and number of people impacted by the breach, and the clauses that have been specified in the Bill.

15 Vendanta Chairmen Says Their \$5 Billion Made-in-India Chip Will Be Ready in 2.5 Years

Vedanta group chairman Anil Agarwal on Friday said that the first phase of its semiconductor project will involve a \$5 billion (roughly Rs. 41,300 crore) investment of the overall \$20-billion (roughly Rs. 1,64,500 crore) outlay, and the venture will be ready with made-in-India chip in two and a half years.

Vedanta is talking to three companies to rope them in as technology partners for its mega plans entailing foundry, chip manufacturing, and packaging and design.

"In 2.5 years, we will give you Vedanta made-in-India chips," Agarwal told reporters on the sidelines of the SemiconIndia 2023 event.

Unknown Facts

 The first alarm clock only rings at 4 a.m.

 The world's first computer mouse was wooden, not plastic.

 No one yet has verified the identity of Bitcoin's founder.

 The word technology was coined in 330 BC by the one and only Aristotle.

Did You Know

News of the Month

Chandrayaan - 3 : India's historic Moon Mission lifts off successfully

The BBC's Arunoday Mukharji, who was at the launch site, said there were roars of "Bharat Mata ki jai [Victory to mother India]" from every corner of the hall.

"Chandrayaan-3 has begun its journey towards the Moon," Indian Space Research Organisation (Isro) chief Sreedhara Panicker Somanath said in his first comments following the successful lift off. "Our launch vehicle has put the Chandrayaan on the precise orbit around the Earth." Isro tweeted that "the health of the spacecraft is normal".

Prime Minister Narendra Modi said Chandrayaan-3 had "scripted a new chapter in India's space odyssey".

The third in India's programme of lunar exploration, Chandrayaan-3 is expected to build on the success of its earlier Moon missions

Chandrayaan-2 - which also comprised an orbiter, a lander and a rover - was launched in July 2019 but it was only partially successful. Its orbiter continues to circle and study the Moon even today, but the lander-rover failed to make a soft landing and crashed during touchdown. It was because of "a last-minute glitch in the braking system", explained Mr Annadurai.

Mr Somanath has said they have carefully studied the data from the last crash and carried out simulation exercises to fix the glitches.

Chandrayaan-3, which weighs 3,900kg and cost 6.1bn rupees (\$75m; £58m), has the "same goals" as its predecessor - to ensure a soft-landing on the Moon's surface, he added.

FREE FASHIONABLE COURSES AVAILABLE ON INTERNET TO ENHANCE YOUR SKILL LIST

Prompt Engineering

Prompt engineering involves designing input instructions to guide AI models like me in generating desired outputs effectively.

Prompt Eng

Data Structure and Algorithms

DSA stands for "Data Structures and Algorithms," which are foundational elements in computer programming for organizing data and solving problems efficiently.

DSA

React

React is an open-source JavaScript library for building user interfaces on the web. It allows developers to create reusable UI components that update efficiently, improving performance and user experience.

React

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning

AI is the concept of creating smart machines, while ML is a subset of AI focused on teaching computers to learn from data and improve their performance on tasks.

Machine learning

AI

Artificial Intelligence Appreciation Day

Artificial Intelligence Appreciation Day is celebrated on July 16 each year. The day aims to honour artificial intelligence technology's positive contributions to humanity. It also highlights AI ethics and encourages conversation about AI and ethics.

What is AI

AI, or Artificial Intelligence, is when computers are programmed to do tasks that typically require human thinking, like learning, problem-solving, and decision-making. It's like teaching machines to think and act smartly.

What accomplishments has AI achieved thus far

1. Natural Language Processing (NLP)

- Language translation (Google Translate).
- Chatbots and virtual assistants (like Siri, Alexa, and Google Assistant)
- Sentiment analysis to understand emotions in text.

2. Computer Vision

- Object recognition and image classification (identifying objects in photo)
- Facial recognition (unlocking phones with your face).
- Autonomous vehicles (self-driving cars).

3. Gaming

- Game playing AI (Deep Blue beating chess champions, AlphaGo winning at Go).

4. Healthcare

- Medical image analysis (detecting diseases from X-rays and scans).
- Drug discovery and development.

5. Finance

- Algorithmic trading in the stock market.

6. Personalization

- Recommendation systems (suggestions on Netflix, Amazon, etc.).
- Content generation (AI-written articles, music, art).

7. Robotics

- Industrial automation and manufacturing.
- Social robots assisting in various tasks.

8. Research and Science

- Data analysis in various scientific fields.
- Protein folding prediction and bioinformatics.

9. Art and Creativity

- AI-generated art, music, and poetry.

10. Education

- Adaptive learning platforms.
- Language learning apps.

Power BI

AI Lifecycle

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AUGUST 2023

MONTHLY
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WELCOME TO DIGITAL AND TECHNICAL WORLD

01 Lapsus\$ Hacker Targeted Uber, Revolut, Grand Theft Auto Maker, London Jury Finds

A London jury has convicted a teenage Lapsus\$ hacking group member for breaching Uber, fintech company Revolut, and blackmailing Grand Theft Auto developers. The hacker targeted Revolut, obtaining data from around 5,000 customers, and then Uber, resulting in nearly \$3 million in damages. Subsequently, the individual hacked Rockstar Games and threatened to release the source code for the upcoming Grand Theft Auto sequel through a Slack message to all Rockstar staff.

02 Scientists employ AI to predict brain cancer outcomes

Stanford Medicine researchers have created an AI model to evaluate stained images of glioblastoma tissue. This model predicts tumor aggressiveness, identifies genetic characteristics, and assesses post-surgery cancerous cell presence, aiding in the treatment of this aggressive brain cancer with a typically short life expectancy. The AI analyzes histology images, which are dyed disease tissue pictures, to provide valuable insights for doctors and scientists.

03 Meta to launch AI model for writing computer codes

Meta Platforms said, it would release an artificial intelligence (AI) model designed to assist in writing computer code, furthering its push into the new technology.

Code Llama, which will be available for free, can write code based on human text prompts and can also be used for code completion and debugging, the social media giant said in a blogpost.

Code Llama supports the popular coding languages like Python, Java and C++ and is not recommended for general text tasks, Meta said

Regulators give green light to driverless taxis in San Francisco

04

California regulators have granted approval to both Cruise and Waymo, two competing robotaxi companies, to operate their autonomous vehicles around the clock throughout all of San Francisco and charge passengers for their services. This decision enables people in San Francisco to book and ride in driverless taxis, introducing automated competition to traditional taxi and ride-sharing services.

05 Microsoft Removing WordPad from Windows After 30 Years

Microsoft has decided to stop updating WordPad and will remove it from future Windows releases.

The software giant will instead recommend Microsoft Word, its paid word processor that has always been far more feature rich than the basic WordPad app that has shipped as part of Windows since Windows 95 and Windows Notepad for plain text documents like .txt.

06 Meta is shutting down Messenger Lite for Android in September

Meta is shutting down Messenger Lite, its lightweight stripped-down version of Messenger, the company confirmed to TechCrunch. Users of the app are starting to see a message that advises them to “use Messenger to keep chatting.” The app has been removed from the Google Play Store for new users and will no longer be available after September 18 for current users

09 Defcon: Humans Take on AI for Safety

At the Defcon security conference, participants, including hackers and students, engaged in the Generative Red Team Challenge, where they attempted to uncover flaws and biases in AI chatbots and text generation models from major companies like Google, Meta, OpenAI, by completing tasks such as generating false information about US citizens' rights and providing covert surveillance instructions, with the results set to inform AI system improvements while highlighting the growing public concern about AI's societal risks.

Time for Change: The Transparent Tech Renaissance

07

Transparent tech is back in style with glass smartphones like NOTHING, see-through earbuds, and colorful translucent gaming consoles. Even chargers and cables embrace the trend. Time to revisit the past with your old Apple CRT monitor and N64 controller.

Vaccine Database Leak Exposes Indian IDs

10

A journalist discovered a Telegram bot in a channel called "hak4learn" that was providing access to the private data of millions of Indians, including their name, passport number, and date of birth, simply by inputting a phone number or Aadhaar (India's national ID) number. The data seemed to be sourced from India's CoWIN vaccination tracking app with over 1 billion registered users.

08 Apple Watch X: Blood Pressure Tracking Coming Soon

Apple plans to mark the 10th anniversary of its watch with a significant upgrade, the "Watch X." This new device will have a thinner case, a sleeker magnetic band, improved microLED display, and the capability to monitor blood pressure.

11 TCS Wins Athora Transformation Deal

Tata Consultancy Services (TCS) has secured a multi-year contract from Athora Netherlands, a Dutch life insurance and pension provider, to create a new business and IT operating model. This collaboration aligns with Athora Netherlands' Ambition 2025 initiative to become a prominent player in pensions and life insurance. Under this arrangement, TCS will oversee all business and IT operations related to policy servicing.

12 'CBDC and Blockchain': Mukesh Ambani's Jio Financial Services Set to Make Web3 Foray

Mukesh Ambani, one of the world's richest men settled in India's financial capital, is prepared to explore the Web3 arena. The 66-year-old Indian billionaire disclosed his Web3-related plans during the 46th annual general meeting of Reliance Industries (RIL) that was held on Monday. While the Reliance chief aims to keep a distance from highly volatile crypto assets for now, he does plan to explore the fields of blockchain and centralised digital currencies — including the eRupee CBDC — which is currently in advanced trials in India.

PM Modi Backs Rules for Crypto, Says There's No Point in Ignoring Technology

13

Prime Minister Narendra Modi has stressed that a comprehensive set of rules are necessary govern the crypto sector. PM Modi, during an exclusive interview with Business Today said that it is only wise to keep up pace with advancements in the technological sector. The regulation of cryptocurrencies has been among India's top agendas as part of its ongoing G20 Presidency that is scheduled to culminate in December this year. India's finance ministry as well as the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) also deem it important that crypto activities are officially governed.

14 Zepto Becomes First Indian Unicorn in Nearly a Year, Raises \$200 Million in Funding

Indian grocery startup Zepto said on Friday it has raised \$200 million (nearly Rs. 1,650 crore) in fresh funding at a valuation of \$1.4 billion (nearly Rs. 11,560 crore), making it the first startup in the country to cross the billion-dollar valuation mark in nearly a year.

Zepto, which promises delivery of groceries in 10 minutes, was started in 2021 by two 19-year-old Stanford dropouts, and competes with SoftBank-funded Swiggy and Blinkit, which are all betting on fast deliveries in the so-called quick commerce sector. Even among them, Zepto's CEO Aadit Palicha said the company has the quickest average delivery time of 13 minutes.

15 Digital Personal Data Protection Act Will Ensure Firms Handle Data of Indians Legally: IT Minister

Union Minister of State for Electronics and Information Technology Rajeev Chandrasekhar on Thursday said the Digital Personal Data Protection Act (DPDP Act) passed by Parliament recently will make digital companies handle the data of Indian citizens under absolute legal obligation.

Calling the law an important milestone in the cyber law framework, Chandrasekhar said there will be punitive consequences of high penalty and even blocking them from operating in India.

Unknown Facts

 India is one of only three countries that makes supercomputers

 India is one of six countries that launches satellites

 The Bombay stock exchange lists more than 6,600 companies

 Nearly 49% of the high-tech startups in silicon Valley and Washington, D.C. are owned by Indians or Indian-Americans

Did You Know

World Wide Web Day

World Wide Web Day is celebrated on August 1 every year. The day is observed to commemorate the World Wide Web (www) and its impact on the world. It was on August 1 in 1991 that Tim Berners-Lee posted a proposal for the World Wide Web on the alt.hypertext newsgroup; this day is, therefore, celebrated with great importance every year. The year 1989 marked the beginning of the Internet. From that point forward, it has continued to evolve.

Examples of World Wide Web

Wikipedia (www.wikipedia.org)

Google (www.google.com)

YouTube (www.youtube.com)

LinkedIn (www.linkedin.com)

Amazon (www.amazon.com)

Reddit (www.reddit.com)

Facebook (www.facebook.com)

Netflix (www.netflix.com)

Facts

The first website went live in 1991 and went public in 1993.

The first websites only had words and pictures.

World Wide Web is not the same as the Internet.

info.cern.ch. was the world's first website.

There are 1.13 billion websites in the world but 82% of them are inactive.

More than 3 billion people all over the world surf the web daily.

The name "Web" was decided after "Information Mesh", "The Information Mine", and "Mine of Information".

Jean Armour Polly, a librarian, is attributed with coining the term "surfing the web".

The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) is the international standards organization for the World Wide Web

China has the most active web surfers, followed by India and USA

News of the Month

Chandrayaan-3 : India make a historic landing near Moon's South Pole

India has made history as its Moon mission became the first to land in the lunar south pole region. The Vikram lander from Chandrayaan-3 successfully touched down as planned at 18:04 local time (12:34 GMT). Celebrations have broken out across the country, with Prime Minister Modi saying "India is now on the Moon". Indian Space Research Organisation (ISRO) chief S. Somnath said successful landing "is not our work alone, this is the work of a generation of Isro scientists".

In terms of technology, Chandrayaan-3 is built with cutting-edge technology. The spaceship, lander and rover are loaded with high-quality components. For those you are unfamiliar the Chandrayaan-3 consist of three parts:- a lander (Vikram), a rover (Pragyan) and a propulsion module. The Propulsion system will remain in orbit for years and will be capable of carrying out variety of experiments.

Chandrayaan-3 has sent Earth its first image of the moon captured during lunar descent ,after its historic soft landing on the lunar south pole on August 23 2023. The Lander Horizontal Velocity Camera captured these images during decent .

NEW IN TECHNOLOGY

SMART RINGS

Smart ring is a wearable electronic gadget with cutting-edge mobile components that combine mobile device functions with unique features practical for handheld or mobile use. Smart rings, which are often the size of traditional rings or larger, combine well-liked novel uses like gesture control and activity tracking with the functionality of a mobile device, such as the ability to make payments and mitigating access control.

Uses Of Smart Rings

- Through a number of applications and websites, smart rings can communicate directly with smartphones or other suitable devices. Some smart rings incorporate capacitive or physical buttons that can be used to activate features like gestures or phone calls.
- One of the fundamental functions of the smart ring is that it acts as a near-field communication device, effectively removing the need to carry identification documents like ID cards or driver's licenses as well as credit cards, door keys, and car keys.

- Other applications include connecting to a smartphone to alert the user of incoming calls, texts, emails, and more; using gesture-based controls to let the user carry out numerous tasks with a single hand motion; and measuring steps, distance, sleep, heart rate, and calorie intake.

DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTER APPLICATION
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WELCOME TO DIGITAL AND TECHNICAL WORLD

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01

Windows 11 Update Unleashes Copilot, AI Magic, and More!

Microsoft is rolling out a significant update for Windows 11, featuring Windows Copilot integration, AI enhancements for Paint, Snipping Tool, and Photos, RGB lighting support, a revamped File Explorer, and more. Windows Copilot brings Bing Chat to the desktop, while developers gain access to Dev Home for simplified Windows dev machine setup, utilizing Microsoft's Windows Package Manager (winget) for streamlined app and tool installations.

02

Raspberry Pi 5: Next-Level Speed and 4K Dual Display Awesomeness

Raspberry Pi 5

The upcoming Raspberry Pi 5, set to launch in October, boasts significant improvements over its predecessor. With a quad-core Arm Cortex-A76 CPU clocked at 2.4GHz and a VideoCore VII GPU running at 800MHz, it offers remarkable speed gains, especially in graphics performance. Additionally, it features dual HDMI outputs for dual 4K displays (60Hz with HDR support), two USB 3.0 ports, two USB 2.0 ports, and Gigabit Ethernet.

03

ChatGPT Expands Horizons: Internet Access Enabled!

OpenAI's ChatGPT is getting a significant update, allowing it to access the internet for current and credible information. This capability was recently announced on OpenAI's official X (formerly Twitter) account, enabling ChatGPT to provide up-to-date information with direct source links. Though you need to subscribe it first.

The Future of Air Travel: Joby Aviation's Air Taxi Milestone

Joby Aviation, an air taxi start-up, sent its aircraft to Edwards Air Force Base in Southern California for the first supersonic flight. Air taxis work like helicopters but also have wings to fly like planes. NASA will test the Joby aircraft, looking at air traffic, flights, and infrastructure from 2024. The goal is to plan how future air transportation systems will work together.

04

05

Meta's Threads: From Boom to Search for New Users

Meta's Threads experienced a remarkable surge, with over 100 million users joining within just 5 days of its launch. However, this initial momentum has decreased, and the platform now faces challenges in attracting new users. Principal Analyst at Insider Intelligence, suggests that Threads cannot solely rely on Twitter defectors (users switching from X to Threads) to drive continued growth.

06

Popular Apps Gather More Data Than Needed, NordVPN Reveals

New research by NordVPN shows that up to 74% of popular mobile apps collect excessive data, surpassing what's necessary for their functionality. This study examined the top five apps in 18 categories for Android and iOS. Many of these apps request access to unrelated device functions, and users often grant permission without reading terms and conditions, warns NordVPN's cybersecurity advisor, Adrianus Warmenhoven.

09

Enhanced Ray-Ban Smart Glasses by Meta

Meta unveils Ray-Ban smart glasses with improved audio, a 12 MP camera, and Qualcomm Snapdragon AR1 Gen1. They're water-resistant, with an enhanced touchpad, and prioritize livestreaming to Facebook or Instagram with real-time comments. Integrated with Meta AI, they're voice-controlled with "Hey Meta."

Meta's Quest 3: Bridging the Gap with Mixed Reality

On October 10th, Meta is set to launch the Quest 3, its newest virtual reality headset. Priced at \$499, the Quest 3 offers expected upgrades such as a higher-resolution display and an improved processor for the leading VR gaming console. However, what sets it apart is Meta's push into "mixed reality" (MR), a term that, typically refers to a video feed overlaid with digital objects passed through to a headset display.

07

Medium Takes a Stand on Content Exploitation by AI

Web publishing platform Medium is taking action to block OpenAI's GPTBot, an agent used to scrape web content for AI model training. This signals the potential formation of platforms that may soon form a unified group against what many consider an exploitation of their content.

10

08

Adobe Raises the Prices with New AI Features

Adobe (ADBE.O) has introduced generative AI features in its software after extensive testing. These features, including image generation from text, are now available. Adobe plans to raise prices while compensating contributors for their AI work. Adobe is known for products like Photoshop, central to its Creative Cloud subscription service.

11

India's Plan: 5 Million Jobs in Tech Manufacturing

India's Minister of State for Electronics and Information Technology, Rajeev Chandrasekhar, recently mentioned that India's efforts in expanding its tech sector manufacturing are expected to generate approximately 5 million jobs in the coming three years. He highlighted that prominent companies like Apple and Micron are actively seeking reliable partners and favorable economic environments. This push for tech sector manufacturing in India is part of the country's ambitious goal to grow its electronics industry to a \$300 billion valuation.

12 India Sees Sharp Drop in Tech Funding in Q3 2023

In Q3 2023, India's tech funding dropped for the third time in a row. It was the lowest in five years, with only \$1.5 billion raised, down 29% from the previous quarter and 54% compared to Q3 2022. Late-stage funding decreased by 33%, while early-stage and seed-stage funding fell by 74% and 75%, respectively, compared to the same quarter last year.

Source: Yourstory

Precision Meets Innovation: iPhone 15 Pro Welcomes India's NavIC

The Apple iPhone 15 Pro series now supports India's NavIC satellite system, developed by ISRO. NavIC offers more precise information, accurate timings, and valuable forecasts, which the Indian government believes can be crucial in critical situations. The government aims to encourage other smartphone manufacturers to incorporate NavIC into their devices by 2023.

13

14 Safety First: Google's Android Earthquake Alerts for India

Google's earthquake alert system for Android devices in India utilizes smartphone sensors as seismometers, developed in partnership with NDMA and NSC. It offers early alerts in local languages with two types: "Be Aware" and "Take Action." These alerts are triggered for MMI 5+ shaking during a 4.5 magnitude quake, overriding notification settings and playing a loud alert sound.

15 Google at 25: From Garage to Global Giant

Google recently celebrated its 25th anniversary. It started as a project called "BackRub" by students Larry Page and Sergey Brin at Stanford University. They got a \$100,000 investment and worked from a garage. Now, Google is a huge tech company with popular products like YouTube, Android, Gmail, and Google Maps. Important moments include AdWords, Gmail offering 1GB storage, and buying Android and YouTube. Sundar Pichai, Google's boss, is excited about AI (smart computers). In the next 25 years, Google will need to keep inventing to stay at the top, especially in AI.

Unknown Facts

A single cloud can weigh over 1 million pounds.

Combining all the bitcoin mining operations worldwide is equivalent to the computing power of 3.7 million supercomputers.

Dead skin cells are a main ingredient in household dust.

The tallest mountain in the solar system is Olympus Mons, which is located on Mars. It is about three times taller than Mount Everest.

News of the Month

Aditya-L1: India successfully launches its first mission of the Sun

Aditya L1 Mission will be first solar mission that will study **Sun** for nearly 5yrs. The **ISRO** PSLV rocket spacecraft is lifted off from (SDSC SHAR), Sriharilota at 11:50(indian-time)

Aditya-L1 Parking Spot
Lagrange Point

Major Objective's:

- Coral Heating & Solar Wind Acceleration.
- Coupling & dynamic of solar atmosphere.
- Solar wind distribution and temperature anisotropy.

Lagrange Point are the position in space where the Gravitational forces of two body (like the Sun and the Earth) creates pockets of Equilibrium. These can be used by spacecraft to stay docked in a single position without requiring to burn fuel

321 Tonne PSLV-XL carried Aditya L1 rocket to Earth's orbit.

Its length is 44.4 meter.

Why is the study of Sun important?

Just as our Earth is in the solar system, Sun is its center. All eight planets revolve around the Sun. Life on earth is possible due to the Sun. Energy continuously flows from the Sun. We call them charged particles. After studying about the Sun it can be seen that changes to the Sun can effect the life in space and on Earth.

The Journey of Aditya L1 in 5 points

1

PSLV rocket ejected Aditya L1 in 235 x 19500 Km orbit of the Earth

2

16 Days
it will remain in Earth's orbit. It will fire thrusters 5 times to increase orbit

3

Again thrusters will be fired and it will depart towards the L1 point

4

After **110 days** of journey, Aditya will reach the point L1

5

Aditya will be put in the L1 point through thruster firing

Aditya L1 reached the orbit

National IT Professional Day

We celebrate National IT professional day on the third Tuesday of every September, on September 19 this year, to recognize the technical experts- Network Engineers, system administrators, database admins , and many more types of I.T professionals that make sure our computer run smoothly. It takes a solid set of skills and talent to fill the shoes of I.T professional

History Of National IT Professional Day

National I.T. Professional Day was created in 2015 in an effort to show appreciation for the tech wizards who take care of the nuts and bolts so that the average worker's station stays hooked up to the company network and operates flawlessly.

Technology has practically advanced at the speed of light since then and someone has always had to keep up with the latest technical advent in order to manage any misfires in a given system. These guys and gals are nothing less than essential to successful business practices.

National IT Professional Day Timeline

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WELCOME TO DIGITAL AND TECHNICAL WORLD

01

Microsoft Shuts Industrial Metaverse Project Airsim to Focus on AI, Lays Off Team Members

Microsoft has discontinued its Airsim project, an AI-based drone simulation software for its industrial metaverse initiative. The decision led to layoffs for the project's team members, though the exact number of affected employees remains unclear. Microsoft emphasizes its ongoing commitment to Azure as the computing platform for the industrial metaverse and other AI projects. In addition to Airsim, the company also recently withdrew support for the Bonsai project, which aimed to develop autonomous systems for industrial use using AI. Both Airsim and Bonsai were integral to Microsoft's efforts to compete with Amazon Web Services in the industrial metaverse space.

02

Elon Musk's Neuralink Receives Approval to Start Brain Implant Human Trial for Paralysis Patients

Neuralink, Elon Musk's brain-chip startup, has received approval to recruit participants for the first human trial of its brain implant for paralysis patients. This trial is open to individuals with paralysis caused by cervical spinal cord injury or ALS. The study will involve surgically placing a brain-computer interface implant in the brain region responsible for intention to move. The initial aim is to enable participants to control a computer cursor or keyboard using their thoughts. The number of patients approved by the FDA remains undisclosed due to safety concerns, after Neuralink initially sought to implant its device in ten patients. The company has ambitious plans to address various conditions, such as obesity, autism, depression, and schizophrenia with its chip devices.

03

Meta Proposes Monthly Fee of Up to EUR 13 for Ad-Free Access to Instagram and Facebook

Meta is exploring the possibility of offering an ad-free version of Facebook and Instagram in certain countries to comply with privacy regulations. Users in the European Union may be able to pay a monthly fee of up to EUR 13 for this ad-free access. The plan, known as "subscription no ads" (SNA), is under discussion with privacy regulators in Belgium and Ireland. However, users in the US and other regions may not have access to this option in the near future.

Spotify Premium Adds Free Access to Audiobooks in Australia and the UK

Spotify is providing 15 hours of free audio book access to its premium users in the UK and Australia, with plans to expand this feature to the US later in the year. This move is part of Spotify's efforts to diversify its revenue streams, including podcasts and audiobooks, which put it in competition with Amazon's Audible. Spotify has ambitious goals of reaching one billion users by 2030 and achieving \$100 billion in annual revenue, with a focus on high-margin returns from its expansion into podcasts and audiobooks.

04

05

WhatsApp Testing Pinned Messages in Group Chats; Working on Username Picker and IP Address Protection

WhatsApp is testing a new feature in its beta version, allowing users to pin group chat messages to the top for up to 30 days. This feature is currently available to select testers using WhatsApp beta for Android version 2.23.21.4. Users can pin messages by long-pressing them, making them easily accessible even as new messages arrive. WhatsApp is also working on a username picker and enhanced privacy features for calls.

06

British School Employs AI Robot As Principal Headteacher For Enhanced Decision-Making

Artificial intelligence is taking over many jobs by automating tasks that were once done by humans. This is happening in a variety of industries, including manufacturing, customer service, healthcare, and transportation. In a surprising move, a preparatory school in the United Kingdom has named an AI robot as its "principal headteacher." Cottesmore School, located in West Sussex, collaborated with an artificial intelligence developer to design Abigail Bailey, the robot, with the purpose of assisting the school's headmaster.

09

WhatsApp Introduces Multiple Accounts on Android: Here's How to Enable the Feature

Add Multiple Accounts on WhatsApp

WhatsApp is introducing a feature for Android users that allows them to have two active accounts simultaneously without logging out. To set up a second account, users need a second phone number and can do so in the app's settings. This change enables users to switch between work and personal accounts seamlessly and adjust privacy and notification settings separately for each account. Messages on both accounts remain end-to-end encrypted. This feature eliminates the need to carry two phones for separate accounts and enhances convenience.

Ferrari Goes Pro-Crypto, Decides to Accept Bitcoin, ETH, USDC Payments for Its Cars

07

Ferrari

Ferrari will now accept payments in Bitcoin, Ether, and USD Coin for its luxury cars in the US, responding to market demands and engaging with a younger, crypto-interested audience. The company plans to extend this payment option to Europe in the near future. BitPay will serve as Ferrari's payment gateway, converting crypto payments into fiat currency for US dealers and monitoring transactions for illicit activities.

ChatGPT Integration in Cars Is a Reality Thanks to DS Automobiles

10

DS Automobiles, owned by Stellantis, has become the first auto company to integrate the ChatGPT AI chatbot into its vehicles. Initially, this feature will be offered to the first 20,000 registered users in a pilot phase lasting six months. To access the AI chatbot, users must have DS 3, DS 4, DS 7, or DS 9 vehicles equipped with an active DS IRIS system and can engage with it by saying "OK IRIS" via a dedicated button on the steering wheel. This integration is available at no extra cost for the initial 20,000 users who purchase qualifying vehicles between October 19 and February 29. It's limited to European regions, including France, Germany, the UK, Spain, and Italy, with support for the national languages of these countries.

08

Elon Musk's X to Test \$1 Annual Subscription Fee for Liking, Reposting and Quoting Posts

The social media platform formerly known as Twitter, now X, is testing a \$1 annual subscription called "Not A Bot." It covers basic features like likes, reposts, quoting, and bookmarking posts on the web version. The goal is to combat bots and spammers. New users who don't subscribe will have limited functionality, but existing users are not affected. This test is being rolled out in New Zealand and the Philippines, and the subscription fee varies by country. X CEO Linda Yaccarino had previously discussed plans for different subscription tiers based on ad exposure. Elon Musk, who acquired the company, has indicated removing the block feature while retaining the mute function.

11

Crypto Rug-Pulls Affect Thousands of Users in Himachal Pradesh, Over Rs 200 Crore Lost

Fraudsters in Himachal Pradesh minted a series of a crypto coins -two of which were KRO and DGT - to cheat thousands of investors of more than Rs 200 crore over a period of five years, beginning in 2018 — the year that crypto reached fever pitch. The persons alleged to be part of a gang lured people promising them high returns in a short span of time in crypto investments and created a network of investors.

12 India Sees Sharp Drop in Tech Funding in Q3 2023

Reliance Industries is introducing swappable and multipurpose battery technology for electric vehicles (EVs) that can also power household appliances. The company is investing heavily in clean energy projects as part of a \$10 billion initiative, aiming for net-zero carbon emissions by 2035. These batteries can be exchanged at Reliance's swap stations or recharged using rooftop solar panels. While not manufacturing EVs, Reliance plans to partner with EV makers, aligning with the Indian government's efforts to promote cleaner transportation through swappable battery technology.

India-Led G20 Adopt Roadmap on Crypto Assets Suggested by IMF, FSB Joint Synthesis Paper

At a recent meeting in Marrakesh, the G20 Finance Ministers and Central Bank Governors adopted a global roadmap for regulating cryptocurrencies. This roadmap emphasizes coordination, regulations, and mitigation strategies with a focus on the impact on Emerging Markets and Developing Economies (EMDEs). The goal is to ensure that crypto assets do not disrupt the stability of existing financial systems. The G20 members are calling for coordinated implementation of the roadmap, global cooperation, data sharing, and support for FATF standards on crypto assets.

14 ISRO Successfully Launches Gaganyaan Test Flight Abort Mission

ISRO Chairman S Somanath confirmed the success of the 'TV-DI' in the Gaganyaan Mission, following a second launch attempt due to an initial engine ignition issue. The mission aimed to demonstrate the crew escape system for the Gaganyaan program, which performed effectively. The crew module separated safely from the vehicle and touched down at sea, achieving its objectives.

15 Amazon Seeks Regulatory Approval to Launch Project Kuiper Satellite Internet Services in India

Amazon is preparing to introduce its satellite-based broadband service, Project Kuiper, in India. The company is in the process of obtaining necessary licenses from Indian government agencies to provide broadband access using a constellation of 3,236 low Earth orbit (LEO) satellites. The service aims to deliver fast and affordable internet, particularly in rural and underserved areas. Amazon has applied for regulatory approval from IN-SPAcE and will need a GMPCS license from the Department of Telecommunications (DoT). The company plans to launch half of the satellites by 2026. More details, including pricing and system requirements, are expected by the end of 2024.

Unknown Facts

 There are 4000 luxury cars sunken in the Atlantic Ocean in 2022.

 Reading from a screen slows your reading time.

 The first computer virus was named 'Creper.'

 The word "robot" originated from a Czech word that means "forced labor."

News of the Month

Indian Mobile Congress 2023 : PM Modi inaugurate Asia biggest three days telecom Event

The 7th edition of the India Mobile Congress (IMC) 2023, which started Friday, has attracted many participants and visitors who are eager to witness the future of digital transformation. A mega event, the IMC showcases trends and innovations in the telecom, media, and technology sectors.

Here are key highlights and announcements from India Mobile Congress 2023.

1. Triggering Innovation –

100 5G labs across India IMC 2023 was the arena in which Hon'ble Prime Minister Narendra Modi announced the setting up of 100 5G labs across India, with the aim of encouraging students, professors, startups and MSMEs to work on 5G technology.

2. Futuristic Solutions from Telecom Operators -

At IMC 2023, telecom operator Airtel demonstrated the capabilities of Airtel 5G Plus in optimizing traffic systems, enabling real-time road monitoring, and enhancing road safety by early accident detection and traffic congestion prevention. It also emphasized the role of Airtel IoT and Airtel 5G network in new connected ecosystems, particularly in supporting OEMs with real-time analytics for safer driving

3. Global Innovations Made a Mark-

At IMC 2023, semiconductor company Qualcomm associated with Ericsson and Airtel to successfully demonstrate Reduced Capability (RedCap) device capabilities, which are expected to boost mid-tier 5G use cases going ahead. The technology was displayed using Qualcomm Snapdragon X35 5G Modem-RF System, in tandem with Ericsson's RedCap software, while leveraging Airtel's 5G TDD network. Further, MediaTek, another leading global fabless semiconductor company, showcased the MediaTek Dimensity Auto Cockpit Solution designed for automobiles.

4. Government Organisations Mark Their Presence-

The preeminent event brought to fore the presence of government and public sector units like RailTel, PowerGrid, Ministry of Heavy Industries, and Ministry of Railways, among others. These organizations highlighted the application of technology and telecom across various use cases, with Power Grid, a Maharatna public sector enterprise, depicting its expertise in transmission, renewable integration and telecommunications.

5. Educational Institutes as the Forefront of Transformation

IMC also witnessed robust participation from many premier educational institutes such as IIT Delhi, IIT Roorkee, IIT Jodhpur, IIT (ISM) Dhanbad, BITS Pilani, NIT Tiruchirapalli, VIT and regional universities. Accordingly, the Gati Shakti Vishwavidyalaya, a central university under Ministry of Railways, highlighted its capabilities in the transportation and logistics sectors, in addition to depicting its academic program in AI and data science

What is E-waste?

Electronic waste (e-waste), is all types of old, end-of-life or discarded electrical and electronic equipments i.e televisions, computers, mobile phones and any type of home appliance, from air conditioners to children's toys.

What are the harms?

With the increase in E-waste Kidney, Liver and Heart diseases are increasing and E-waste does contains hazardous materials, predominantly lead and mercury, and is produced by businesses, governments, and industries.

E-waste in the world

5.74 Crore

metric tons of E-waste was found.

2021

20 Lakh metric tonne is increasing every year.

34.7 Crore

metric tons of E-waste unrecycled.

2023

Maximum recycling is done by Estonia, Norway and Iceland

\$4988 Crore

was the E-waste in recycling market

2020

Earth Sinking under E-waste

Electronic waste (E-waste) or Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) represent a major environmental challenge in the world today. It represents discarded appliances with a battery or a plug. Rapid advances in technology, economic growth, urbanisation processes, increasing demand for consumer electronic equipment and a downward trend in prices are a few factors responsible for the unparalleled growth of E-waste worldwide during the last two decades.

E-waste in India

A survey by Accenture and Indian Cellular and Electronic Association (ICEA) came out last week on how serious the problem of e-waste has become in India. It revealed that in Indian homes more than 20 crore smartphones, Laptops and other gadgets are lying idle.

States collecting E-waste

ICEA has given some suggestions in its report which will help in disposal of garbage and increase employment opportunities.

- Product development as a service.
- Strong spare parts and supply chain should be made, to increase sales after service.
- Eco-design essentials should be prioritized.
- Market development of recycled materials and establishment of renewal standards,
- Insurance/Warranty should be mandatory.
- Promotion of high capacity waste recycling facilities.
- By gathering in targeted places Solution areas should be formed.
- Find out the mechanism for formal consumer withdrawal.

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WELCOME TO DIGITAL AND TECHNICAL WORLD

01

Tech Titans Testify on Child Safety

A significant Senate hearing slated for January 31st, 2024, will feature prominent tech figures discussing online child exploitation. Meta's Mark Zuckerberg, X's Linda Yaccarino, TikTok's Shou Zi Chew, Snap's Evan Spiegel, and Discord's Jason Citron are set to testify. Notably, Zuckerberg and Chew volunteered for this session. The focus will be on addressing their alleged shortcomings in safeguarding children on digital platforms.

Tech Titans job board

Search openings across our network

02

Capsule: AI-Enhanced News Discovery

In a bid to revolutionize daily news consumption, Parisian startup Capsule introduces an innovative app. Unlike typical news aggregators, Capsule aspires to be the "Spotify for news," employing a fusion of AI and human editorial curation. This distinctive approach transforms diverse sources, including news articles, newsletter snippets, and social media updates, into easily digestible information within their user-friendly app.

03

Google's Problem-Solving Upgrade: Math Made Easy!

Google has boosted its search engine and Lens tool with advanced capabilities to tackle complex subjects like geometry, physics, trigonometry, and calculus. With this update, users can input equations into the search bar or utilize Lens to snap a photo, receiving not only the correct answer but also a step-by-step breakdown. This feature even extends to solving word problems, offering a comprehensive math-solving experience.

Saudi Arabia Levels Up: Gaming's New Crown Prince

04

Saudi Arabia wants to be a big player in gaming, planning to become a major center for gaming and esports. Saudi Arabia is aiming to become a gaming "powerhouse" - a hub for development and esports. With support from Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman, their wealth fund has invested in top gaming companies like Nintendo, Take-Two, EA, and Activision Blizzard. They aim to become a significant part of the \$187 billion gaming industry.

05

OpenAI's Assistants API: Powering Better Apps!

OpenAI unveiled the Assistants API, a tool empowering developers to create "agent-like experiences" within their apps. This API allows customers to craft an "assistant" equipped with specific instructions, harnessing external knowledge and utilizing OpenAI's generative AI models to execute tasks.

The Assistants API adds extra info to developer-built assistants, like product details or company documents. It also allows function calling, making it more versatile for app development.

06

DeepMind's AlphaFold Advancement in Drug Discovery

DeepMind, renowned for AI research under Google, introduced AlphaFold, an AI that accurately predicts human body protein structures. An upgraded version, AlphaFold 2, has since been enhanced. The latest iteration, AlphaFold's successor, can predict structures for almost all molecules in the Protein Data Bank. Beyond proteins, the new model extends its prowess to predicting ligand structures—molecules altering cell communication by binding to receptor proteins. This development holds significant promise for drug discovery. [Sounds Crazy]

Sony's Fight Against Fake Images: 'In-Camera Authenticity'

Sony has announced a partnership with the Associated Press and Camera Bits to combat AI-manipulated images through the development of 'in-camera authenticity' technology. This innovation aims to tackle image falsification by introducing a digital signature, essentially creating a birth certificate for images to verify their origin. Sony plans to roll out this feature in 2024 via a firmware update for its Alpha 9 III, Alpha 1, and Alpha 7S III models.

08

GTA VI: Rockstar's Long-Awaited Revelation

After a decade and two console generations since GTA V's release, Rockstar is finally prepared to unveil GTA VI to the world. The gaming giant announced the release of the game's first trailer, scheduled for Tuesday, December 5th, 2023, at 6 AM PT / 9 AM ET. This announcement triggered a domino effect across game studios, with many adopting Rockstar's minimalist image and text style, adorned with soft sherbet colors, as a template for their own announcements.

09

Amazon's Palm Tech Goes Beyond Payments

Originally for cashier-free payments, Amazon's palm scanning tech now shifts focus to office security. Rebranded as Amazon One Enterprise, it's tailored for workplaces. Employees can use this biometric system to access buildings, computers, and sensitive information by scanning their palm. This move extends the tech's reach from grocery stores to corporate offices for enhanced security and access control.

Altman's Emotions and OpenAI's Mission: A CEO's Journey

In an interview with The Verge, Altman shared his initial mix of emotions—defiance, hurt, and anger—after his CEO reinstatement. He admitted it took a moment to move past ego and emotions to embrace the change, expressing deep love for the company. Altman emphasized his dedication to OpenAI's mission of making AGI safe and beneficial, citing the company's remarkable progress.

Regarding comments about misunderstandings between him, the board, and Chief Scientist Ilya Sutskever, Altman declined to comment further, stating he wasn't ready to discuss it and expressing unawareness of Sutskever's intentions.

10

11

India Awaits VoNR: 5G's Missing Voice Technology

Voice over New Radio is not yet available in India. This, even as leading carriers continue rolling out 5G across major cities. There's been no official announcement from Reliance Jio, Airtel, Vi, or any other operator about an impending VoNR launch, suggesting widespread availability is still quite far off. Reports indicate Reliance Jio, India's largest mobile carrier, has been testing VoNR behind the scenes. The goal is to ensure smooth interoperability between existing 4G VoLTE networks and new 5G infrastructure.

12

Tech Whisperer's Mission: AI for Every Indian

Jaspreet Bindra

The TechWhisperer

In a recent episode of the 'Tech Whisperer Podcast' on indianexpress.com, tech entrepreneur Jaspreet Bindra revealed an ambitious plan to create India's own extensive language model for generative AI. This model aims to be a digital public asset, accessible to India's vast population of 1.4 billion, mirroring existing public digital infrastructure like payments and identity systems.

NASA to Train Indian Astronaut for ISS Mission

NASA's administrator, Bill Nelson, announced during his visit to Delhi that the US space agency plans to train an Indian astronaut for a mission to the International Space Station by the end of 2024. Following a meeting between Nelson and Union Minister Dr. Jitendra Singh, a joint statement from the department of space highlighted discussions on collaborative studies. These include radiation impact, micro meteorite and orbital debris shields, as well as space health and medicine.

13

14

AMD's Mega Design Center Opens in Bengaluru, India

AMD inaugurated its largest global design center, the Technostar research and development campus in Bengaluru, with Union Minister Ashwini Vaishnaw present for the ceremony. Praising the move, the minister stated, "AMD setting up its largest design centre in Bengaluru is a testament to the confidence global companies have in India." The campus includes modern research labs, visitor demo centers, and collaborative spaces. With 25% of AMD's global workforce in India, this new facility positions the Indian design center as a key contributor to semiconductor advancements.

AMD
RYZEN

15

HP Gaming Study 2023: Serious Gamers Earning Big in India

HP India's latest Gaming Study delves into the Indian gaming market, revealing a significant rise in earnings for gamers. Compared to 2022, almost half of the "serious gamer" respondents now claim annual earnings between Rs 6-12 lakh in 2023. Covering insights from 3,000 gamers across 15 major Indian cities, the study highlights a notable shift in attitudes toward gaming. Players are increasingly driven by financial rewards and recognition.

Unknown Facts

The first Apple logo isn't what you would think.

There's a name for when you feel your phone vibrate... but it doesn't.(Phantom Vibration Syndrome)

Everyone uses Google as a spellchecker.

The first word to ever be auto-corrected was "teh." to Ten

News of the Month

Amazon announces new cloud AI chip to compete with Microsoft Nvidia and AMD

Amazon has unveiled an artificial intelligence (AI) chip, called Trainium2, to train large language models, at the re:Invent conference in Las Vegas. The development comes as other tech companies and chipmakers, including Microsoft, Nvidia and AWS have launched their processors.

Amazon claimed that the Trainium2 chip is capable of delivering up to 4x faster training than first generation Trainium chips and it offers up to 2x energy efficiency.

Companies will be able to deploy these chips in Amazon Compute Cloud (Amazon EC2) Ultra Clusters (up to 100,000 chips)

Trn2 instances are intended to enable customers to scale up 100,000 Trainium2 chips in next generation EC2 Ultra Clusters, interconnected with AWS Elastic Fabric Adapter (EFA) petabit-scale networking, delivering up to 65 exaflops of compute and giving customers on-demand access to supercomputer-class performance," the company said.

Amazon will start offering the Trainium2 chips next year. The company will continue to offer access to Nvidia's latest H200 AI graphics processing units.

Amazon launches AWS Graviton4

Amazon also announced Graviton 4 chip which is the company's most powerful and energy-efficient AWS processor to date for a broad range of cloud workloads. According to the company, Graviton4 provides up to 30% better compute performance, 50% more cores and 75% more memory bandwidth than current generation Graviton3 processors.

Microsoft's Maia 100 chip

The development comes a few weeks after Microsoft unveiled the Microsoft Azure Maia 100 AI chip at Ignite 2023. The chip is optimised to handle AI tasks and generative AI. It also announced Microsoft Azure Cobalt CPU, an Arm-based processor to run general purpose compute workloads on the Microsoft Cloud.

The Maia 100 is the first in a series of Maia accelerators for AI, the company said. With 105 billion transistors, it is "one of the largest chips on 5-nanometer process technology," referring to the size of the smallest features of the chip, five billionths of a meter.

National Computer Security Day

Every year on November 30th, we commemorate National Computer Security Day to raise awareness of the importance of cybersecurity in our day-to-day activities. It started out as a reaction to the increasing risks in cyberspace, with the goal of raising awareness and motivating people and organizations to use best practices for protecting their digital assets. As we approach National Computer Security Day in 2023, the importance of securing our digital landscape becomes increasingly evident. In an era defined by technological advancements, connectivity, and digital dependency, the need to prioritize computer security has never been more critical.

National Computer Security Day 2023 provide a chance for educational programs and awareness campaigns, in addition to underscoring the significance of cybersecurity. The goal of outreach initiatives, webinars, and workshops is to provide people and organizations with the information they need to safely traverse the digital world.

In conclusion, National Computer Security Day 2023 encourages us to consider the significance of cybersecurity in our daily lives and to take preventative action to safeguard our digital assets and self. Let's work together to make sure that creativity, connectivity, and security—above all—are hallmarks of our digital future.

Key Themes for National Cyber Security Day 2023

Empowering user education with knowledge is fundamental to cyber resilience. Initiatives aimed at educating individuals about safe online practices, recognizing phishing attempts, and securing personal information are at the forefront.

For businesses, the emphasis is on building robust cybersecurity policies and practices. Ensuring the security of customer data, implementing secure communication channels and fostering a cyber-aware workforce are vital components of business continuity.

Cyber threats often transcend sectors and borders. National Cyber Security Day encourages collaboration between government agencies and the private sector to share threat intelligence, best practices, and jointly address cyber challenges.

With the rapid adoption of emerging technologies like artificial intelligence and the Internet of Things, integrating security measures into these innovations is imperative. The day promotes responsible and secure development and deployment of cutting-edge technologies

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December
2023

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DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTER APPLICATION

TECHNICAL COMMITTEE

1

Data of 200 million twitter users leaked

Hackers stole the email addresses of more than 200 million Twitter users and posted them on an online hacking forum, a security researcher said on Wednesday, 4 January 2023. The breach "will unfortunately lead to a lot of hacking, targeted phishing and doxing", Alon Gal, co-founder of Israeli cybersecurity monitoring firm Hudson Rock, wrote on LinkedIn. He called it "one of the most significant leaks I've seen". Twitter has taken to investigate or remediate the issue. Reuters could not independently verify if the data on the forum was authentic and came from Twitter. Screenshots of the hacker forum, where the data appeared and have circulated online.

3

PM Modi unveils 6G test bed, industry hails move

After a successful 5G rollout in the country, Prime Minister Narendra Modi on Wednesday announced the Bharat 6G vision document and launched the 6G research and development (R&D) test bed.

Inaugurating the new International Telecommunication Union (ITU) area office and innovation centre during a programme at Vigyan Bhawan here, he said that the 6G R&D test bed will help faster adoption of the new technology in the country. The government said that the Bharat 6G vision document and 6G test bed will provide an enabling environment for innovation, capacity building, and faster technology adoption in the country.

The industry hailed the PM's move to roll out the 6G test bed in the country. "6G holds the possibility to provide extreme speeds with predictably low latency and a low jitter rate for high demanding scenarios and about 10Cr active 6G devices by 2030," said Arvind Bali, CEO, Telecom Sector Skill Council (TSSC). "By providing a platform for academic research, industry, and startups, the 6G Test Bed can pave the way for the development of skilled and innovative workforce," he added. In August last year, PM Modi had said that the government is preparing to launch 6G by the end of this decade.

Indian government blocked 232 Betting and Loan apps that are linked to China and other countries

2

The government has blocked 232 apps operated by overseas entities, including Chinese for being involved in betting, gambling and unauthorized loan service. Ministry of Electronics and IT (MeitY) has issued orders to block these apps following instructions from Ministry of Home Affairs. The order to block 138 apps that were involved in betting, gambling and money laundering were issued last evening. Separately, an order to block 94 apps engaged in unauthorised loan service has also been issued. They were posing a threat to the economic stability of the country.

Model created using AI and tweets to help early detection of mental disorders

4

Work is underway to create anxiety and depression prediction models, using artificial intelligence (AI) and Twitter, one of the world's largest social media platforms that could detect signs of these illnesses before clinical diagnosis, according to researchers. Researchers at the University of São Paulo (USP) in Brazil said that preliminary findings from the model suggested the possibility of detecting the likelihood of a person developing depression based solely on their social media friends and followers.

5

A camera without lens ? Paragraphica generates images using location data & AI

Introducing Paragraphica, the world's first context-to-image camera that visualises a photo based on location data and AI. The camera comes as a physical unit and a virtual camera that users can try. According to the official website, the camera works by collecting location data with the help of open APIs (application programming interfaces). It uses information such as time of the day, address, weather, and places in the vicinity. Paragraphica writes a paragraph based on the combination of all these details.

8

Scientists employ AI to predict brain cancer outcomes

Stanford Medicine researchers have created an AI model to evaluate stained images of glioblastoma tissue. This model predicts tumor aggressiveness, identifies genetic characteristics, and assesses post-surgery cancerous cell presence, aiding in the treatment of this aggressive brain cancer with a typically short life expectancy. The AI analyzes histology images, which are dyed disease tissue pictures, to provide valuable insights for doctors and scientists.

AI Supercomputer 'AIRAWAT' puts India among top supercomputing league

6

The International Supercomputing Conference (ISC 2023) in Germany, the AI Supercomputer 'AIRAWAT', situated at C-DAC, Pune, achieved an impressive global ranking of 75th on the esteemed Top 500 Global Supercomputing List. This accomplishment establishes India as a leading nation in the field of AI supercomputing. 'AIRAWAT' is part of the Government of India's National Program on AI and represents a significant stride forward in the country's AI capabilities.

Future of Air Travel: Joby Aviation's Air Taxi Milestone

9

Joby Aviation, an air taxi start-up, sent its aircraft to Edwards Air Force Base in Southern California for the first supersonic flight. Air taxis work like helicopters but also have wings to fly like planes. NASA will test the Joby aircraft, looking at air traffic, flights, and infrastructure from 2024. The goal is to plan how future air transportation systems will work together.

7

First US Robotic Liver Transplant: A Medical Milestone!

A surgical team from Washington University School of Medicine in St. Louis achieved a remarkable milestone by performing the first-ever robotic liver transplant in the United States. This groundbreaking procedure, carried out at Barnes-Jewish Hospital, brings the advantages of minimally invasive robotic surgery to liver transplants, offering promising benefits for future patients in need of this life-saving procedure.

10

ISRO Successfully Launches Gaganyaan Test Flight Abort Mission

ISRO Chairman S Somanath confirmed the success of the 'TV-D1' in the Gaganyaan Mission, following a second launch attempt due to an initial engine ignition issue. The mission aimed to demonstrate the crew escape system for the Gaganyaan program, which performed effectively. The crew module separated safely from the vehicle and touched down at sea, achieving its objectives.

11

Amazon's Palm Tech Goes Beyond Payments

Originally for cashier-free payments, Amazon's palm scanning tech now shifts focus to office security. Rebranded as Amazon One Enterprise, it's tailored for workplaces. Employees can use this biometric system to access buildings, computers, and sensitive information by scanning their palm. This move extends the tech's reach from grocery stores to corporate offices for enhanced security and access control.

14

India's Aditya-L1 Solar Probe Launches Toward the Sun

India has successfully launched its first space-based solar observatory mission – just 10 days after the landing of its spacecraft Chandrayaan-3 on the lunar south pole.

India's space agency, the Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO), has installed seven payloads on the Aditya-L1 spacecraft, four for remote sensing and three for on-site experiments.

Meta's Threads: From Boom to Search for New Users

12

Meta's Threads experienced a remarkable surge, with over 100 million users joining within just 5 days of its launch. However, this initial momentum has decreased, and the platform now faces challenges in attracting new users. Principal Analyst at Insider Intelligence, suggests that Threads cannot solely rely on Twitter defectors (users switching from X to Threads) to drive continued growth.

13

4-British School Employs AI Robot As Principal Headteacher For Enhanced Decision-Making

Artificial intelligence is taking over many jobs by automating tasks that were once done by humans. This is happening in a variety of industries, including manufacturing, customer service, healthcare, and transportation. In a surprising move, a preparatory school in the United Kingdom has named an AI robot as its "principal headteacher." Cottesmore School, located in West Sussex, collaborated with an artificial intelligence developer to design Abigail Bailey, the robot, with the purpose of assisting the school's headmaster.

Companies paying up to 1.5 crore to ChatGPT experts

15

A Business Insider report also says that companies on LinkedIn are willing to pay up to USD 185,000 (around Rs 1.5 crore) per year to people having expertise in the use of ChatGPT.

For instance, Recruiting from Scratch, an HR company based in the US, is hiring for the position of Senior Machine Learning Engineer, Audio and the skills required for the job include 'Familiarity with current AI tools and platforms - ChatGPT, Midjourney and others'.

AI Changed the Internet in 2023

Pushed “DEEPPFAKES” into the mainstream

Deepfakes, or media that's been altered by AI to seem real, have been a concern for some time. But this year, the widespread availability of generative AI tools made it easier than ever to conjure up realistic images, videos, and audio. OpenAI, Google Bard and Meta's Imagine are all examples of models that use generative AI to create images from text prompts.

Gave “HALLUCINATION” a new meaning unrelated to drugs

This was the year everyone learned computers could hallucinate, too — just not in a fun or transcendental sort of way. Hallucination is when generative AI confidently fabricates its responses, giving it the illusion of believing something that isn't true. AI hallucinations often make sense linguistically, and sometimes contain elements of reality.

Introduced us to AI-GENERATED content

One of generative AI's amazing capabilities is writing natural-sounding language. Currently, most AI-generated content reads like that of a high school student that didn't do all the reading — prone to inaccuracies and slightly robotic. But with time, LLMs are getting better, making the automation of articles, press releases, job listings, and creative works.

Raised the alarm about TRAINING DATA

How did LLMs get so good? They're trained on the entirety of the internet. Everything — Reddit posts, social media posts, Wikipedia pages, hundreds of thousands of pirated books, news sites, academic papers, YouTube subtitles, food blogs, memes — feeds the AI models' insatiable appetites.

POPULAR DEBUGGING TOOLS OF 2023

TOP MOST TECHNOLOGY TRENDS IN 2023

- 1 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE**
Artificial intelligence is the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, especially computer systems.
- 2 METAVERSE**
The metaverse is a loosely defined term referring to three-dimensional virtual worlds in which users represented by avatars interact.
- 3 BLOCKCHAIN**
Blockchain technology is an advanced database mechanism that allows transparent information sharing within a business network.
- 4 QUANTUM COMPUTING**
A quantum computer is a computer that takes advantage of quantum mechanical phenomena.
- 5 CYBER SECURITY**
Cybersecurity is the practice of protecting systems, networks, and programs from digital attacks.
- 6 CLOUD COMPUTING**
Cloud computing applications used by both businesses and individuals.
- 7 DATAFICATION**
Datafication is turning various facets of your life into digital data.
- 8 HYPERAUTOMATION**
Hyperautomation aims for end-to-end automation across all processes, workflows, systems, bots, and tools.
- 9 GREEN COMPUTING**
Green computing, green IT, or ICT sustainability, is the study and practice of environmentally sustainable computing.
- 10 IOT(InternetofThings)**
The internet of things is a technology that allows us to add a device to an inert object.
- 11 SUSTAINABLE TECHNOLOGY**
It is an umbrella term that describes innovation that considers natural resources technology.
- 12 5G NETWORKS**
5G is the fifth-generation technology standard for cellular networks.

10 MOST POPULAR CODING LANGUAGE OF 2023

